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Title:

**“Voices from the Margins: How the People of
Barangay 175 Perceive the Effects
of Sustainable Development”**

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APPROVAL SHEET

This thesis entitled **“VOICES FROM THE MARGINS: HOW THE PEOPLE OF BARANGAY 175 PERCEIVE THE EFFECTS OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT”** prepared and submitted by **MARIA VERONICA S. BOTIAL, AZELL ANN A. DIAMSE, JASHKLEISH GONZAGA, WINSTON P. MORALES,** and **JAMES ROFEL NAING** in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of Bachelor of Science in Business Administration Major in Human Resource Development has been examined and is recommended for acceptance and approval.

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Approved and accepted in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of
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CERTIFICATION OF ORIGINALITY

This is to certify that the research work presented in this thesis entitled “BEHAVIORAL PSYCHOLOGY AND HR: IMPACTS ON PRODUCTIVITY AND WELL-BEING IN BRGY. 175 AT NORTH CALOOCAN CITY” for the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration Major in Human Resource Management at the University of Caloocan City embodies the results of original and scholarly work carried out by the undersigned. This thesis does not contain words or ideas taken from published sources or written works that have been accepted as basis for the award of a degree from any other higher education, institution, except where proper referencing and acknowledgement were made.

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Abstract

TITLE : “*Voices from the Margins: How the People of Barangay 175 Perceive the Effects of Sustainable Development*”

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This study examined the impact of inconsistent execution of sustainable development projects in Barangay 175, focusing on residents’ awareness, experiences, and perceived effects on the community. Using a qualitative research design, data were collected through interviews with selected residents to gather in-depth insights regarding the implementation of barangay programs. The findings revealed that many residents have limited awareness of sustainable development projects, often due to lack of visibility and communication from barangay officials. While some initiatives such as educational assistance, environmental programs, and infrastructure projects were identified, these were frequently described as delayed, rescheduled, or inconsistently implemented.

Furthermore, the inconsistent execution of projects resulted in several challenges within the community, including poor waste management, flooding risks, inadequate infrastructure, transportation difficulties, and disturbances caused by ongoing or incomplete construction. Although some residents expressed indifference toward these issues, others highlighted their negative effects on daily living conditions, safety, and overall quality of life.

The study concludes that inconsistent project implementation not only limits public awareness and trust in barangay governance but also hinders the effectiveness of sustainable

development efforts. It is recommended that the barangay improve project planning, strengthen communication and transparency, ensure continuity of programs, and actively engage the community to achieve more effective and sustainable development outcomes.

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Chapter 1

THE PROBLEM AND ITS BACKGROUND

This chapter provides a comprehensive introduction to the study, including its background, the problem statement, objectives, and the significance of the research.

Introduction

Sustainable development has become a central goal of governments and institutions worldwide, particularly at the local level where policies and projects directly affect people's everyday lives. In communities, sustainable development projects are designed to improve quality of life by addressing social, economic, and environmental needs in a balanced and long-term manner. At the barangay level, these initiatives often take the form of livelihood programs, infrastructure improvements, environmental efforts, and social services intended to uplift communities and promote inclusive growth. As the smallest unit of local government, the barangay plays a crucial role in translating national and global development goals into concrete actions that reach ordinary citizens.

Despite the growing emphasis on sustainability, questions remain about how these development projects are actually experienced by the people they are meant to serve. While projects may appear successful on paper, their real impact is best understood through the perceptions of community members, especially those whose voices are often overlooked. Marginalized groups frequently face barriers such as limited access to information, unequal participation, or inadequate representation in decision-making processes. In this context, good governance and social responsibility require not only the implementation of sustainable projects but also the active inclusion of community voices in evaluating their effects.

Understanding people's perceptions is particularly important in assessing whether sustainable development initiatives truly respond to local needs. Community members are in a unique position to describe how projects influence their daily lives, whether these initiatives address existing challenges, and whether they contribute to a sense of inclusion and shared responsibility. Without listening to these perspectives, development efforts risk becoming top-down interventions that fail to achieve meaningful and lasting outcomes. This gap between project implementation and lived experience highlights the need for research that centers community voices, especially those from the margins.

This study addresses this gap by exploring how the people of Barangay 175 perceive the effects of sustainable development projects implemented in their community. Anchored on the principles of good governance and social responsibility, the research seeks to give space to residents' experiences, insights, and concerns regarding these initiatives. By focusing on perceptions rather than numerical indicators alone, the study aims to provide a deeper understanding of how sustainable development efforts are received at the grassroots level and how they shape community well-being.

The findings of this study are expected to contribute to a better understanding of community-centered development and inclusive governance. By amplifying voices from the margins, the research hopes to inform local leaders, policymakers, and stakeholders about areas where sustainable development projects succeed and where improvements are needed. Ultimately, this study underscores the importance of listening to the people in building development initiatives that are not only sustainable in design but also meaningful and responsive to the communities they intend to serve.

Background of the Study

Sustainable development is a widely recognized approach to addressing long-term social, economic, and environmental challenges, particularly at the community level. It emphasizes meeting present needs without compromising the ability

of future generations to meet their own. In local communities, sustainable development is often carried out through projects initiated or supported by local government units, such as livelihood programs, infrastructure development, environmental protection initiatives, and social welfare services. These projects are intended to promote inclusive growth, improve quality of life, and ensure responsible use of resources.

At the barangay level, sustainable development plays a crucial role in translating national development agendas and global commitments, such as the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), into concrete actions. Barangays serve as the closest governance structure to the people, making them key actors in implementing development initiatives that directly affect community members. In line with the principles of good governance and social responsibility, effective sustainable development requires transparency, accountability, inclusiveness, and responsiveness to the needs of the community. However, the success of these projects is not determined solely by their objectives or completion but also by how they are experienced and perceived by the people they are meant to benefit.

One important concept in assessing sustainable development initiatives is community perception. Perception refers to how individuals understand, interpret, and evaluate the effects of programs or projects based on their lived experiences. In the context of development projects, community perceptions provide valuable insights into whether initiatives address actual needs, promote inclusion, and produce meaningful outcomes. This is especially important for marginalized groups, whose voices are often underrepresented in planning and evaluation processes. Giving attention to these perspectives aligns with participatory governance, which emphasizes citizen involvement in decision-making and evaluation.

Various factors influence how community members perceive sustainable development projects. These include the level of community participation, access to information, transparency of project implementation, and the perceived fairness of resource distribution. When residents are actively involved and informed, they are more

likely to view development efforts as relevant and beneficial. Conversely, limited consultation, poor communication, or lack of accountability may lead to dissatisfaction or distrust, even if projects are well-intentioned. These factors highlight the need to examine development initiatives beyond technical outcomes and consider their social impact on communities.

This study focuses on understanding how the people of Barangay 175 perceive the effects of sustainable development projects implemented in their community. By giving attention to the voices from the margins, the research examines how these projects influence daily living, community participation, and local governance. Through this perspective, the study highlights the role of good governance and social responsibility in ensuring that sustainable development initiatives are inclusive, responsive, and beneficial to the people they are intended to serve.

Statement of the Problem

Many people experiencing challenges come from inefficiency of some projects made by the government itself. This makes no difference to what the residents of Barangay 175 in Caloocan City encounter when incomes to LGU projects lead to confusion, unmet expectations, and erosion of trust toward local authorities. These things happen despite the positive narrative reports written and posted to different social media platforms which differ from the lived experiences of the people.

Unleading actions result in issues that show how the marginalized people are often overlooked in evaluating the real impact of the government's said efforts about sustainability. With that, the researchers come up with the thoughts of what are the possible reasons that these unfortunate things happen; due to poor allocation of resources or due to the unhinged use of financial budgets? According to PIDS, the Madanas ruling, which substantially raised the fiscal autonomy of Local Government Units (LGUs), brought to the forefront the challenges LGUs face in managing their financial resources effectively.

This research will focus to the following problems:

1. What is the perception of the residents of Barangay 175 in Caloocan City about the Sustainable Development Projects carried out by the Local Government Units (LGUs)?
2. What have been the experiences of the people of Barangay 175 with the implementation and sustainability of Sustainable Development Projects in their area?
3. How do residents describe the impact of the inconsistent execution of Sustainable Development Projects on their daily activities and the overall quality of the community?
4. What obstacles do residents link to the gaps in the Sustainable Development related initiatives in Barangay 175?
5. In what ways do these gaps affect the community's trust, engagement, and general view of local government?
6. What do residents recommend to enhance the planning, execution, and longevity of future development initiatives in their barangay?

These problems will seek answers to light and illuminate the gaps between policy and project intentions to our lived community experiences.

Scope and Limitations

The study will be conducted in Barangay 175, Caloocan City, with respondents consisting of selected residents of the barangay. As a qualitative research, the study will involve approximately 5 to 10 participants, who will be chosen to provide in-depth insights through interviews regarding their perceptions of sustainable development projects implemented in their community.

The scope of this study focuses on understanding how residents perceive the effects of sustainable development projects in terms of social, economic, and community-related outcomes. It centers on the voices and lived experiences of

community members, rather than on the technical design, funding, or implementation process of the projects themselves.

This study is limited to Barangay 175 only and does not include other barangays or cities. It also does not assess the perspectives of local government officials, project implementers, or policymakers. Additionally, the study does not aim to measure long-term impacts or provide a quantitative evaluation of project effectiveness, as it relies on qualitative perceptions and narratives of the resident

Significance of the Study

This study highlights the experiences and perspectives of the community to the issues made by the questionable actions or projects of our LGU. By focusing on the voices of residents from Barangay 175, this research provides an in-depth understanding of how development projects are perceived beyond official reports and policy intentions. It also seeks answers on how effective the projects are based on its effect and the possible reasons why it is not successful at all.

Local Community - This study enables residents to articulate their worries, hopes, and encounters with sustainable development initiatives.

Local Government Units (LGU) - The findings of this study can offer valuable insights into the gaps between planned development goals and actual community outcomes.

Development Practitioners/Planners - This research contributes to a deeper understanding of the social impacts of sustainable development projects at the grassroots level.

Students and Future Researchers - This study contributes to the growing field of qualitative research on sustainable development and community attitudes in the Philippines. It may serve as a reference for similar studies focusing on marginalized communities, local governance, and participatory development approaches.

Chapter 2

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

This chapter presents reviews of related literature and studies which are related literature and studies, theoretical framework and the paradigm of the study.

Sources like books, encyclopedias, journals, thesis, dissertations and internet materials that deals with the local and foreign literature has been used to gather meaningful insights on how to conduct the relevance of this study.

Related Literature and Studies

Albert, Genio, and Crismo (2025) analyze the evolution of integrated approaches to poverty reduction and social welfare in the Philippines through cooperative or joint programming among government agencies. Their study highlights how coordinated planning and implementation, particularly the bundling of services such as cash transfers, livelihood assistance, employment facilitation, and social services, enable local governments to address the multidimensional nature of poverty more effectively. The authors argue that within integrated development models like the Graduation Model, long-term poverty reduction necessitates comprehensive support packages that enable households to transition out of poverty through a combination of income stabilization, skill development, and market participation. The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), especially SDG 1 (No Poverty), SDG 8 (Decent Work and Economic Growth), and SDG 10 (Reduced Inequalities), must be translated into localized and implementable programs by local government units (LGUs) like Caloocan City. This framework directly supports their mandate. The findings of Albert et al. (2025) are pertinent to Caloocan City because they show how barangay-level beneficiaries experience and view convergence-based programs such coordinated social protection, livelihood training, and employment facilitation initiatives. The study emphasizes the importance of effective coordination mechanisms, shared data systems, and strong local government implementation competence in ensuring that integrated initiatives lead to real changes in inhabitants' daily lives. In contrast, deficiencies in coordination,

overlapping mandates, and poor data interoperability can result in fragmented service delivery, leading to community perceptions of development initiatives as inefficient or detached from local needs. By situating joint programming within national frameworks such as the Philippine Development Plan 2023–2028, the literature reinforces the role of cities like Caloocan in operationalizing SDG-aligned strategies and highlights how residents' perceptions of sustainable development are influenced by the coherence and accessibility of LGU-led interventions.

Fuseini (2024) presents international empirical evidence suggesting that the most visible and impactful benefits of integrated development frameworks are frequently realized through infrastructure expenditures that have a direct impact on community well-being. His study of Ghana's Community-Based Rural Development Programme (CBRDP) shows that combining economic infrastructure (e.g., roads, dams, and market facilities) with social infrastructure (e.g., health centers, water systems, and training facilities) significantly enhances livelihoods by increasing productivity, improving access to essential services, and creating self-employment opportunities. These outcomes directly support the objectives of SDG 9 (Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure), SDG 11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities), and SDG 5 (Gender Equality), which are also central to urban development priorities in Caloocan City. Fuseini's results are relevant to Caloocan City given that they have consequences for how locals perceive LGU-led infrastructure and social services projects. The study shows that infrastructure has a direct impact on daily life, such as lowering healthcare-related transportation costs, limiting job disruptions, and promoting livelihood continuity—factors that are also important in densely populated metropolitan regions. Furthermore, the discovery of gender-differentiated benefits emphasizes the significance of inclusive and gender-responsive planning in city-level programs. However, consistent with the concerns raised by Albert et al. (2025), Fuseini emphasizes that weak maintenance planning and limited community participation undermine long-term sustainability and public trust. For Caloocan City, this suggests that achieving SDG-aligned outcomes depends not only on the presence of integrated programs but also on sustained

community engagement, effective coordination, and inclusive governance structures. Collectively, these studies support the argument that residents' perceptions of sustainable development initiatives in Caloocan City are shaped by how well LGU programs integrate social protection, infrastructure development, and participatory mechanisms in ways that deliver visible, equitable, and lasting benefits.

Distor and Khaltar (2022) investigate the drivers of local government efficiency across 141 Philippine cities, identifying factors that critically shape the delivery of local public services—such as infrastructure, regulatory processes, and community programs—within urban settings like Caloocan City. Their research reveals that institutional capacity, notably technology infrastructure and the availability of competent public service people, plays a critical role in pushing cities to perform more efficiently. This shows that more effective governance structures directly improve the speed, quality, and responsiveness of local development projects. Furthermore, the authors point out that adherence to national public service standards, notably the implementation of streamlined electronic systems, has a favorable impact on efficiency. These developments show how local alignment with higher-level policy frameworks helps to deliver better service outcomes. Importantly, the study emphasizes that efficiency extends beyond technical input/output ratios; it must also include responsiveness to inhabitants' demands. Citizens' perceptions of local government performance are greatly impacted by tangible service improvements, such as quicker business registration, better administrative responsiveness, and organized development planning, as per Distor and Khaltar (2022). This body of research emphasizes how the ability and intentions of local governments affect how the public views sustainable development initiatives. Residents are likely to view projects more favorably in areas with strong institutional capability and policy compliance because of noticeable improvements in service delivery. Ultimately, this study provides a governance lens through which to interpret how the people of Caloocan City view the effects of sustainable development, acknowledging that administrative efficiency and responsiveness are fundamental to public satisfaction and perceived impact.

Valle et al. (2024) argue that one of the primary ways modern cities improve administrative efficiency is through the adoption of digital governance tools, although this shift introduces new challenges related to public trust. In their study of the implementation of e-government technologies in Caloocan City, the authors discovered that digital platforms have significantly reshaped interactions between the local government and its constituents, with 73% of residents satisfied with the system's interface and overall design. This high level of customer satisfaction supports the continuous use of digital tools to improve accessibility and service efficiency. However, the study also finds a continuing "trust gap," with only 58% of respondents reporting confidence in the platform's data security and privacy safeguards, and 10% directly expressing distrust in the system. This finding is consistent with Belanche et al. (2012), who emphasize that trust and personal values are essential components of the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), indicating that technical performance alone is insufficient to sustain long-term adoption when privacy concerns remain unresolved.

Manoharan et al. (2023) further contextualize the significance of Caloocan City's digital initiatives by noting that major Philippine urban centers have historically underperformed in digital governance, particularly in relation to global benchmarks associated with Sustainable Development Goals 9 and 16. The circumstances explain the city's focus on e-government as a strategy for inclusive growth in densely populated areas. Faulkner et al. (2019) argue that citizen-centric digital governance can improve service delivery efficiency and transparency by focusing on user requirements and trust-building processes. Similarly, Dioquino (2023) and Zahid et al. (2022) argue that automation and mobile-accessible platforms are becoming increasingly important in contemporary governance because they allow local governments to reach a larger segment of the population regardless of physical location, reduce reliance on physical infrastructure, and reduce bureaucratic delays. Taken together, these studies suggest that while Caloocan City has made meaningful progress in improving the usability of its digital services, addressing trust concerns through stronger data protection, responsive

customer support, and transparent communication is essential for strengthening public confidence and fostering a more inclusive and cohesive community.

Porio (2015) argues that while digital and administrative efficiency are essential, the broader implementation of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) requires moving beyond macro-level indicators to address localized urban realities. A large portion of the literature on urban sustainability and human well-being, according to Abbas and Erzajj (2020) and Wood and Ashton (2010), advocates for a move away from generalized development frameworks and toward socioeconomically sensitive, localized approaches that represent the actual experiences of urban dwellers. These authors point out that while traditional assessment instruments, like the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs), the United Nations Commission for Sustainable Development (UNCSD) framework, and different Livable Cities Indicators (LCIs), have been successful in standardizing the measurement of global progress, they frequently fall short in capturing internal social differentiation, inequality, and marginalization in rapidly urbanizing areas like Metro Manila. Nigra (2019) further contends that although global development targets are attractive due to their simplicity and perceived attainability, they frequently overlook critical issues of social exclusion, unequal resource distribution, and structural vulnerability that define quality of life (QOL) in cities of the Global South. In order to balance top-down planning mechanisms with community-based self-organization, Rooke and Molloy (2011) and Zhang et al. (2021) emphasize the significance of adaptive governance and the localization of SDG targets. This body of research collectively highlights a growing consensus that decentralized and contextualized sustainability frameworks are necessary in dense metropolitan contexts to maintain the relevance and responsiveness of infrastructure, housing, and health indicators to the needs of the most vulnerable urban populations.

UN-Habitat (2023) emphasizes the importance of global monitoring frameworks in localizing the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), while also highlighting a continuous gap between policy pledges and on-the-ground development. UN-Habitat's SDG Cities Framework offers a comprehensive, data-driven approach to sustainable

urbanization by providing local government units (LGUs) with tools for baseline evaluation, strategic planning, and impact-oriented investment. While cities serve as key engines of economic growth, the framework underlines long-standing problems such as data availability, institutional capability, and resource restrictions, which frequently impede successful localization of global development goals. Allen et al. (2019) and Simon et al. (2016) similarly argue that the translation of national SDG commitments into local action remains uneven, particularly in rapidly urbanizing regions where governance and financing gaps persist. By operationalizing the Global Urban Monitoring Framework (GUMF), the SDG Cities initiative enables municipalities to align evidence-based local actions with national and global agendas, with particular emphasis on strengthening governance systems, urban planning mechanisms, and municipal finance for inclusive development. UN-Habitat (2020) further underscores the importance of Voluntary Local Reviews (VLRs) as instruments of transparency and accountability, allowing cities—such as those in the Philippines—to track progress in alignment with the New Urban Agenda (NUA) and SDGs 9 and 11. In addition, OECD (2020) emphasizes that in order to close the "implementation gap" by connecting high-impact urban projects to international networks of technical expertise and funding, participatory, multilevel governance models—backed by platforms like Urban Labs and digital diagnostic tools—are crucial. In order to maintain resilient, inclusive, and sustainable urban growth, the literature as a whole indicates that the successful localization of the SDGs in high-density urban regions requires striking a balance between top-down national initiatives and bottom-up community involvement.

United Nations (2025) reports that global progress toward the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) has reached a critical turning point, with only 18% of targets on track and more than half showing low to moderate advancement, a situation largely attributed to persistent implementation gaps. According to the documents, this gap is worsened by a lack of comprehensive, disaggregated data that policymakers require to effectively identify and address the needs of vulnerable people, particularly in metropolitan regions. UN-Habitat (2023) similarly notes that while local governments are

constitutionally mandated to deliver basic services, many lack the localized statistical capacity required to identify marginalized groups, as national-level data often obscure sub-national inequalities. This data gap is particularly noticeable in high-density urban areas, where informal settlements and socially excluded people are "invisible" in official reporting systems (OECD, 2020). To address these structural limitations, the literature emphasizes the strategic role of the digital transition in modernizing national and local statistical systems, allowing for the collection of granular, community-level data required for monitoring progress toward SDG 11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities) and SDG 16 (Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions) (UN-Habitat, 2020; Zhang et al., 2021). Moreover, Allen et al. (2019) argue that closing the implementation gap requires not only substantial financial investment—estimated in the trillions annually for urban infrastructure—but also a shift toward multilevel governance frameworks that empower cities to translate global commitments into evidence-based local action. Collectively, the literature underscores that without high-quality, disaggregated data to inform inclusive urban planning and service delivery, the foundational SDG principle of “leaving no one behind” will remain unattainable in rapidly urbanizing regions.

Bantayan et al. (2025) argue that in the Philippine context, the localization of sustainable development necessarily involves addressing environmental vulnerabilities through community-driven resilience strategies. Focusing on the CAMANAVA area—comprising Caloocan, Malabon, Navotas, and Valenzuela—the study demonstrates that integrating disaster-resilient community building serves as a critical driver of both environmental sustainability and socio-economic recovery. Initiatives like the Adopt-the-Tullahan River project are emphasized as efficient ways to reduce the risks of chronic flooding, directly supporting Sustainable Development Goals 11 and 13 while also boosting local tourism and improving the standard of living for locals through community-led Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM). These results support the claim that environmental initiatives are more sustainable when they produce observable social and economic advantages in addition to ecological preservation. The results correspond with Valle et al. (2024), who contend that resilience in high-density

urban areas like Caloocan City should be viewed as a socioeconomic issue that calls for proactive citizen empowerment rather than only a technical or infrastructure issue. In order to ensure that catastrophe mitigation activities effectively impact the community's entire socio-economic health, Bantayan et al. (2025) further underline that effective urban resilience plans must combine environmental preservation and economic vitality. Through the application of local knowledge and the establishment of shared responsibility among citizens, this strategy indicates a shift toward a more integrated model of urban governance, where catastrophe preparedness and inclusive growth are mutually reinforcing. Ultimately, the CAMANAVA experience provides a justified and scalable framework for other flood-prone urban areas in the Philippines, demonstrating that community participation and resilient infrastructure are essential to achieving long-term sustainable urban growth.

Kaputa and Tembo (2024) argue that beyond environmental resilience, the effectiveness of local development projects is strongly influenced by leadership quality and the level of accountability upheld by implementing authorities. They observed that inconsistent leadership and inadequate accountability systems were the main reasons for project abandonment in their analysis of project implementation within a non-governmental organization in Zambia, especially in community-oriented initiatives like livelihood support and clean water provision. According to their findings, inadequate monitoring methods and incompetent leadership frequently lead to misuse of funds, delays in implementation, and insufficient project delivery, all of which undermine community trust. Even though there was community involvement, the report emphasizes that when governance mechanisms are inadequate and accountability procedures are poor, participation alone cannot ensure project success. Because beneficiaries linked failed initiatives to poor management rather than sustainability goals, these governance failings had a detrimental impact on community attitudes. This literature is relevant to the present study on how the people of Caloocan City perceive the effects of sustainable development projects, as it highlights the critical role of

leadership, transparency, and accountability in influencing both project outcomes and public trust in sustainability initiatives.

Sever et al. (2025) further emphasize that effective local leadership must be culturally sensitive and grounded in indigenous values to foster meaningful community ownership. In *The researchers of Sustainable Development Goals in a Transforming World: Understanding the Dynamics of Localization* view SDG localization as an agency-driven transformation, with cities and local governments serving as the main change agents, rather than a top-down administrative process. They contend that localities should be seen as active shapers rather than passive sites of global development objectives, using a grounded theory approach and the Philippines as a major point of reference. In order to achieve long-term impact, the report criticizes the shortcomings of a "one-size-fits-all" approach and argues that SDG implementation must be tailored to local institutional capacity, indigenous knowledge systems, and cultural values. In the Philippine context, this includes integrating sociocultural concepts such as *damay* (shared burden and empathy) and *malasakit* (compassionate care), which serve as indigenous frameworks for social responsibility and community resilience. Sever et al. (2025) warn that neglecting these local dynamics increases the risk of policy failure, whereas leveraging cultural values can enhance community ownership and bridge the gap between global development indicators and local socioeconomic realities.

Yttredal and Homlong (2020) assert that the ultimate measure of localized sustainable development efforts lies in how these initiatives are perceived by residents, as such perceptions are closely tied to the extent to which projects address immediate, everyday needs. The authors' analysis of the Geirangerfjord World Heritage site shows how local opinions of sustainability are highly context-dependent and largely influenced by issues that have an immediate impact on everyday life and the environment. According to their findings, stakeholder opinions are frequently shaped more by social factors than by environmental or economic ones, especially when it comes to issues of community stability and settlement continuity. This focus supports the claim that locals

assess sustainability using concrete factors that facilitate daily life, such as steady work, safe housing, and long-term communal viability, rather than abstract global metrics. Yttredal and Homlong further explain that in densely populated urban contexts, citizens tend to interpret global sustainable development goals through a localized lens, where the “basis for thriving and living” becomes the primary benchmark of success. The introduction of the “What Is Not There” (WINT) analytical approach reinforces this point by identifying gaps in local discourse, showing that residents may deprioritize broader global interdependencies in favor of immediate and visible benefits. This perspective provides a strong justification for adopting inclusive development and effective governance strategies (SDGs 9 and 16) that are grounded in contextual empathy. For a city such as Caloocan, this implies that digital tools and policy interventions must be intentionally designed to respond to the specific socio-economic needs and security concerns articulated by the community. Ultimately, the study underscores that because place of living strongly influences how sustainability is understood, local governments must actively align global development frameworks with localized perceptions to bridge the gap between policy objectives and meaningful public engagement.

Villanueva, Cruz, and Tan (2021) emphasize that the effectiveness of livelihood programs at the barangay level is primarily determined by the perceived practical benefits of the intervention rather than by administrative indicators such as funding size or program duration. In their study on sustainable livelihood initiatives in urban barangays, they found that community-based programs are more likely to succeed when beneficiaries recognize their direct usefulness in addressing immediate economic needs. This finding suggests that livelihood interventions become truly sustainable when they align closely with the day-to-day realities of participants, as positive perceptions of a program’s utility encourage continued participation and foster local ownership. The authors' focus on "actual usefulness" is consistent with more general development viewpoints that contend that top-down financial allocations frequently fail to have long-lasting effects when the skills or resources given do not result in stable and continuous economic activities for marginalized households. Additionally, incorporating

livelihood programs into barangay-level structures allows for more accurate evaluations of local resources and capabilities, guaranteeing that interventions are incorporated into urban impoverished communities' socioeconomic fabric rather than serving only as temporary relief measures. In order to successfully promote sustainable development goals at the local level, the study emphasizes the necessity for policymakers and local leaders to give needs-based planning and functional relevance precedence over capital-intensive projects.

According to Sulasula (2024), a comprehensive governance strategy that prioritizes openness, citizen participation, and institutional innovation is necessary for effective local leadership in the Philippines. In order to ensure that policies and programs are both legitimate and responsive, inclusive governance and active community consultation are essential tools for coordinating administrative goals with public acceptance. In the study titled "Best Practices in Barangay Governance: A Case Study of the Zamboanga Peninsula Region, Philippines," the author identifies that "transparency in budgeting"—specifically through the open publication of financial reports and the use of social media for public communication—serves as a fundamental driver of community trust and accountability. The study emphasizes that public consultations and "regular community assemblies" are essential tools for participatory governance that provide locals a sense of involvement in the decision-making process. According to this research, constituents' perceptions of the efficacy and impact of local projects greatly increase when they are given the opportunity to express their concerns and participate in the formulation of policies in both urban and rural barangays. This alignment with SDG 16 (Peace, Justice, and inclusive societies) implies that the inclusiveness of the governance process has a greater bearing on the perceived success and subjective value of community initiatives, like health services or disaster management, than does the actual amount of funding allotted. Ultimately, the study concludes that fostering such inclusive frameworks not only strengthens democracy at the grassroots level but also enhances the overall resilience and efficiency of local government units.

Rabia (2025) establishes that active community participation is a decisive factor in determining both the success and perceived impact of sustainable development projects, particularly in island barangays in the Philippines. According to the study, locals gain a strong sense of ownership when they are actively involved in the planning and execution phases, which boosts acceptance and favorable opinions of development projects. This result supports the claim that involvement turns development from being seen as an external imposition into a shared community benefit that is intimately related to local socioeconomic realities. On the other hand, Rabia discovers that the lack of real consultation causes community members to feel excluded, which leads to underutilization of project resources and pervasive views of project failure. These outcomes provide empirical support for the shift away from top-down governance models toward participatory approaches that are responsive to the unique social and geographic conditions of island communities. Furthermore, the study emphasizes that barangay-level participation enables development programs to address context-specific vulnerabilities more effectively, particularly in areas such as marine resource management and the creation of alternative livelihoods. Development interventions become more socially acceptable as well as more environmentally and economically sustainable over time when local knowledge and community priorities are included into decision-making processes. Because it emphasizes how inclusive participation boosts project legitimacy, improves resource utilization, and promotes sustained community engagement, all crucial components in attaining long-lasting and locally supported development outcomes. This literature is extremely pertinent to research on community perceptions of sustainable development.

Simon et al. (2024) in their research titled "Spatializing the SDGs", argue that the implementation of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) at the sub-national level often faces critical tensions when global frameworks encounter the daily challenges of global urbanization. The authors state that when SDG 11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities) is localized, it is often filtered through market-driven urban planning that prioritizes aesthetic modernization over inclusive growth. According to this literature, the

urban poor often view "sustainable development" as a tool for gentrification and state-led displacement rather than inclusive growth, particularly when greening or infrastructure initiatives lead to the removal of informal settlements. In which marginalized communities view official SDG success indicators—like better public spaces or updated waste management—as direct challenges to their land tenure and existence. The study comes to the conclusion that SDG 11 runs the risk of being used as a means of excluding the very individuals it seeks to protect if localization efforts do not specifically include the "right to the city" for vulnerable communities. This highlights the exclusion of under represented groups, which turns growth from an advancement into a perceived danger. This framework emphasizes the necessity of participatory governance that treats the urban poor as essential stakeholders rather than obstacles to development, providing a critical lens for evaluating whether localized projects in areas like Barangay 175 are viewed as genuine improvements or as instruments of exclusion

According to the study of Pierreto and Camana (2023), a sustainability maturity assessment can be used to evaluate plans, programs, and initiatives in order to set improvement goals and strategies that address different dimensions of sustainability. This framework helps connect the present condition of a community with its desired future state, enabling more dynamic and effective sustainability management at the local level. This study is relevant to the present research because it emphasizes the importance of local-level sustainability efforts and community participation, which are also central to this study. Similarly, the present research focuses on the perception of residents in a barangay setting regarding the social, economic, and environmental effects of sustainable development initiatives.

Sustainability has long been practiced, even in ancient societies, particularly in rural communities. Hariram (2023) highlighted that early cultures often linked environmental preservation with religious or cultural beliefs, encouraging people to care for the natural world and maintain balance in their surroundings. Understanding the historical roots of sustainability provides a foundation for examining how modern communities perceive and practice sustainable development. In the context of this

study, the focus is on how residents in Barangay 175 perceive sustainability initiatives and their social, economic, and environmental effects. The enduring concept of sustainability—caring for resources over time—relates directly to the residents' role in supporting and participating in development programs that aim for long-term community well-being.

Bedso (2025) Conducted among professors in Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in Baguio City found that instructors have only an average level of awareness of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), indicating limited depth in integrating sustainability into their teaching. Although educators recognized the importance of SDGs, they faced challenges such as lack of resources, insufficient training, time constraints, and heavy workloads, which hindered effective implementation. The study emphasized the need for stronger institutional support and professional development to enhance sustainability integration. This finding shows that limited awareness and support can also affect sustainability practices and perceptions among residents in the barangay 175 or local community setting.

Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) play a vital role in advancing the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs); however, their use of e-learning as a platform for embedding sustainability remains underexplored in the Philippine context. Atento (2025) revealed that while digitalization is widely adopted, it is often viewed primarily as a practical tool for instructional continuity rather than as a strategic avenue for promoting sustainability education. This gap highlights the limited integration of sustainability concepts into digital learning environments. This suggests that insufficient emphasis on sustainability education whether in academic or digital platforms may also be reflected at the community level, where residents' awareness, experiences, and perceptions of social, economic, and environmental sustainability within the barangay setting may likewise be influenced by the availability of accessible and meaningful sustainability information and programs.

Youth empowerment serves as a key indicator of inclusive governance, as it reflects the active participation of young people in shaping community development. In the context of this study, the involvement of youth in creating community plans demonstrates their role as agents of sustainable development within the barangay setting. Bastida, et. al., [2024] revealed that youth participants prioritized goals related to clean sanitation, quality education, gender equality, good health and well-being, peace, and strong institutions, which highlights their strong orientation toward social welfare and governance. However, the lower emphasis on climate action, decent work, economic growth, and partnerships for the goals indicates a gap in addressing broader environmental and economic dimensions of sustainability. This imbalance may influence residents' perceptions of community development efforts and suggests the need for more holistic youth engagement programs that integrate all pillars of sustainable development.

The United Nations' 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) 2030 provide a comprehensive framework for addressing global challenges and guiding sustainable development efforts at both national and local levels. Among these, Sustainable Development Goal 16 on Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions plays a crucial role in achieving other development goals, as it promotes accountable governance, access to justice, and inclusive decision-making. On SDG 16 implementation, Camorongon (2023) reveals persistent challenges in meeting its indicators, particularly in ensuring equitable and accurate access to information, as well as strengthening transparency and accountability mechanisms within institutions. These issues are highly relevant in the context of barangay or local community settings, where governance structures directly affect service delivery, social equity, and development outcomes. Limited access to reliable information and weak institutional transparency may influence how residents perceive the effectiveness of local governance and sustainability initiatives.

Modern management plays a significant role in advancing sustainable development, as its application of knowledge, planning, and leadership practices contributes to improving the overall well-being and functioning of society. According to Berić, et. al., (2020), Effective management supports the development of communities by promoting efficient use of resources, participatory decision-making, and the strengthening of human capital. In the context of sustainable development, modern management emphasizes the integration of knowledge, skills, and social values that guide individuals and institutions toward responsible and long-term community growth. These principles are highly relevant within the barangay or local community setting, where local leaders and stakeholders implement programs that directly affect residents' quality of life. The presence of effective management practices in community initiatives can enhance social services, economic opportunities, and environmental protection efforts. Consequently, the way these management practices are applied may influence residents' perceptions of governance, inclusivity, and sustainability in their community.

The Philippine STEM senior high school examined students' awareness and integration of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) using a quantitative descriptive approach. Amigable (2025) revealed that formal education serves as the primary source of SDG awareness among students; however, their understanding of the broader temporal and geographic scope of the SDGs remains limited. Padilla (2025) further found that while SDGs are well integrated in subjects such as STEM Research, Social Science, and Science-related courses, gaps exist in disciplines like Mathematics. Moreover, students' knowledge and sources of information were found to significantly influence their learning outcomes, personal engagement, and career planning toward sustainability-oriented paths. These findings are relevant to the critical role of education in shaping individuals' awareness and participation in sustainable development. In the context of the barangay setting, the level of SDG awareness among youth and residents may influence how community members perceive and engage with local sustainability initiatives, governance practices, and development programs.

Examining sustainable project management (SPM) in a developing country context investigated the relationship between SPM and project success, including the moderating effects of stakeholder engagement and team building. Shaukat [2023] revealed that the results indicated that integrating sustainability into project planning and execution positively impacts project outcomes, though stakeholder engagement and team-building effects were found insignificant. Eweje (2023) also emphasizes the importance of considering sustainability throughout all stages of project life cycles to create meaningful social, environmental, and economic value for stakeholders. In relation to the present study, these findings highlight the significance of applying sustainable management principles in community-level initiatives, such as barangay development projects. Incorporating holistic sustainability strategies, fostering participation, and ensuring that project decisions reflect long-term social and environmental considerations may enhance residents' perception of local development programs and improve overall community outcomes.

A related study examined resource optimization strategies in cultural and creative enterprises (CCI) to support sustainable socio-economic development, using a neural network-based recommendation system to model project features and optimize resource allocation. Wang (2023) demonstrated that systematic, data-driven decision-making can significantly improve project outcomes and reduce errors, thereby contributing to long-term sustainable development. Although this study focuses on entrepreneurial enterprises, its findings are relevant to the present research as they highlight the importance of effective resource management, planning, and prioritization in achieving sustainable outcomes. In the context of barangay-level development programs, adopting similar principles of resource optimization and evidence-based planning can enhance the effectiveness of community initiatives, strengthen social and economic impacts, and positively influence residents' perceptions of sustainability efforts.

Public participation significantly influences governance processes and contributes positively to sustainable development outcomes, while effective governance further strengthens the relationship between citizen participation and development. Hongo (2022) emphasized that limited public awareness and access to participation opportunities hinder meaningful community involvement. These findings are relevant to the present study as they highlight the importance of residents' participation and perception in achieving sustainable development at the local level, particularly within barangay communities. The success of sustainable development initiatives in the barangay depends on how residents perceive, understand, and engage in governance processes, as well as how local leaders facilitate inclusive and accessible participation mechanisms.

Rusfiana (2023) found that disruptions in power and weak governance negatively affect public sector performance, which in turn leads to underdeveloped communities. However, strong social connections and trust between government employees and citizens were shown to mitigate these negative effects and promote sustainable cultural and community development. These findings are relevant to the present study as they emphasize the importance of ethical governance, effective leadership, and positive citizen government relationships in achieving sustainable development at the local level. In terms of barangay communities, residents' perceptions of governance transparency, fairness, and service delivery can influence their level of participation and support for community programs. Sustainable development outcomes in the barangay are closely linked to how residents perceive governance practices and how effectively local officials engage with the community in implementing development initiatives.

Gündoğdu and Aytekin (2022) demonstrated that effective and sustainable governance supported by factors such as digital access, political reform, and environmental performance significantly contributes to the achievement of sustainable development goals (SDGs). Which connects to the success of sustainable development at the barangay level depends not only on programs and resources but also on the

quality of governance, ethical leadership, and citizen engagement. On the other hand, local communities, residents' perceptions of transparency, accountability, and service delivery influence their willingness to participate in development initiatives. Thus, these studies support the ideas that effective barangay governance and positive resident perceptions are essential in promoting social, economic, and environmental sustainability in the community

Governance strategies implemented in selected barangays such as Barangay San Jose Gusu, Barangay Talisay, Barangay Dao, and Barangay Poblacion. Sulasula (2024) revealed that transparency in budgeting, active citizen participation, disaster risk management, and the integration of e-governance systems significantly improved service delivery and strengthened community engagement. She also revealed that transparency and participation build trust between residents and local officials, while preparedness and technological innovation enhance efficiency and resilience within the community. Which directly relevant to effective barangay governance practices influence residents' perceptions and participation, which are essential components in achieving sustainable development at the local level. The success of development initiatives in barangay communities depends on how residents perceive governance performance and how actively they are involved in decision-making processes. Transparency, participation, and effective governance practices contribute significantly to the social, economic, and environmental sustainability of local communities.

In Zamboanga City, a study examined governance gaps at the barangay level and their effects on the achievement of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Which identified key governance challenges, including financial instability, leadership turnover, coordination issues, and limited public participation. Zabala (2024) found that these governance gaps significantly hinder the effective implementation of development programs and weaken the capacity of barangays to achieve sustainable social, economic, and environmental outcomes. Financial constraints and leadership instability were found to be the most critical barriers, while limited citizen participation reduced

community engagement and support for local initiatives. Which relates to the success of sustainable development at the barangay level depends on both effective governance and active community involvement. Residents’ perceptions of governance quality, transparency, and service delivery influence their willingness to participate in community programs and support local development initiatives. Strengthening governance systems and enhancing community participation are essential in promoting sustainable development in barangay communities.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

The conceptual framework of this study follows the Input–Process–Output (IPO) model to guide the qualitative examination of residents’ perceptions and recommendations regarding sustainable development initiatives in Barangay 175. The inputs of the study include the socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents, such as age, gender, educational attainment, occupation, and length of residence in the barangay. It also considers residents’ lived experiences and identified community

needs, the existing sustainable development projects implemented in Barangay 175—including infrastructure improvements, livelihood programs, digital services, and disaster-resilient initiatives—and the level of resident engagement in previous development efforts, particularly in terms of consultation and participation.

The process involves conducting in-depth interviews to explore residents' experiences and perceptions of these development initiatives. The collected data are analyzed using thematic analysis to identify recurring patterns and significant themes. This stage also examines the gaps between the intended goals of development projects and the actual experiences of residents, while systematically gathering their recommendations to improve the planning, implementation, and long-term sustainability of future initiatives.

The outputs of the study include a comprehensive understanding of residents' perceptions of the effectiveness of development projects, particularly in terms of their usefulness, relevance, inclusivity, and impact on quality of life. In addition, the study generates actionable recommendations from residents that may serve as a basis for enhancing future development planning, execution, and sustainability in Barangay 175.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This study is anchored on Perception-Based Development Theory (Yttredal & Homlong, 2020), which asserts that the effectiveness of development initiatives is ultimately determined by how individuals and communities perceive and experience their outcomes. Unlike traditional approaches that rely primarily on quantitative indicators or policy measures, this theory emphasizes the subjective evaluation of development projects by the intended beneficiaries.

Perception-Based Development Theory provides a framework for understanding the perspectives of residents in marginalized communities. It asserts that residents' assessments of sustainable development initiatives are influenced by their experiences of usefulness, relevance, inclusivity, and contribution to quality of life. The theory

underscores that perceptions are shaped not only by observable outcomes but also by the degree to which projects address local needs, promote social equity, and enhance daily living conditions.

Applying this framework, the study examines how the people of Barangay 175 interpret the impacts of sustainable development projects within their community. Residents' perceptions serve as a critical measure of project effectiveness, reflecting both the tangible and intangible dimensions of development. By foregrounding the voices of the community, this study aligns with the theoretical premise that sustainable development is meaningful only when it is experienced positively and interpreted as beneficial by its intended stakeholders.

DEFINITION OF TERMS

Barangay – refers to the smallest unit of local government in the Philippines where community-level programs and services are implemented.

Barangay 175 – refers to the specific community in Caloocan City where the respondents of the study reside and where data were collected.

Community Participation – refers to the involvement of residents in planning, implementing, or evaluating development projects in the barangay.

Community Well-being – refers to the overall condition of residents in terms of safety, social relationships, access to services, and quality of life.

Environmental Initiatives – refer to programs and activities that aim to protect the environment, such as waste management, cleanliness drives, and conservation efforts in the barangay.

Good Governance – refers to the practice of transparent, accountable, and participatory leadership in managing community programs and services.

Inclusive Development – refers to development efforts that aim to benefit all members of the community, including marginalized and vulnerable groups.

Marginalized Groups – refer to sectors of the community that may experience limited access to resources, participation, and opportunities.

Perception – refers to the personal views, opinions, and understanding of residents regarding the effects of sustainable development projects in their community.

Public Services – refer to services provided by the barangay or local government such as health programs, sanitation, and social assistance.

Residents – refer to individuals living in Barangay 175 who participated as respondents in this study.

Resource Allocation - The distribution and utilization of financial, material, and human resources for sustainable development projects as perceived by community members.

Social Effects – refer to the perceived influence of development projects on relationships, community cooperation, and social inclusion.

Social Responsibility – refers to the obligation of local leaders and institutions to act in ways that promote the welfare of the community.

Sustainable Development – refers to development initiatives that aim to meet present community needs while preserving resources and opportunities for future generations.

Sustainable Development Projects – refer to programs and activities implemented in the barangay that address social, economic, and environmental concerns.

Voices from the Margins – refer to the experiences and perspectives of community members whose views are often underrepresented in development planning and evaluation

Chapter 3

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This chapter presents the research design utilized, research locale, respondents of the study, data gathering instruments and procedures.

Research Design

The focus of this study is to examine the perceptions and lived experiences of the residents of Barangay 175, Caloocan City regarding the Sustainable Development Projects implemented by the Local Government Units (LGUs), particularly the gaps between policy intentions, project narratives, and actual community experiences. This research makes use of a qualitative research design.

In order to learn how the people in their barangay perceive the planning, execution, and sustainability of development projects, a qualitative approach will be used. Although local authorities have provided encouraging reports, it will examine the misunderstandings, unfulfilled expectations, and decline of credibility that result from the uneven implementation of these changes. People worry about resource allocation and financial management will be among the challenges the study will highlight in relation to gaps in sustainability-related activities. Additionally, the study will collect their suggestions for enhancing future development projects.

The selection of qualitative techniques is supported by its ability to give voice to minority groups and document real-life experiences that are frequently left out of official government assessments. This study uses thematic analysis and comprehensive narratives to provide understanding of the gap between the intended developmental outcomes and their substantial impact on the community's quality of life. The effectiveness of sustainable development and local government can be reconsidered using the key perspective provided by this research.

Population and Sample of the Study

The study population consists of selected residents of Barangay 175, in Caloocan City, who have personal encounters with community-based sustainable development projects. Their points of view are essential for understanding how these activities are viewed and how it affects their daily life.

The study will use purposive sampling. To make sure the respondents have enough knowledge and experience about improvements in the community, total of (10) locals who have lived in Barangay 175 for five (5) years or more will be chosen. Their voluntary involvement will be confirmed by obtaining their informed consent prior to performing the interviews. In-depth interviews will be used to collect data in order to obtain comprehensive insights into their perspectives on sustainable development.

Research Instrument

The researchers will use a semi-structured interview as the primary data gathering instrument in this study entitled “Voices from the Margins: How the People of Barangay 175 Perceive the Effects of Sustainable Development.” An interview is a qualitative method of collecting information through a guided conversation between the interviewer and the interviewee. In this process, the researcher asks open-ended questions, and the participant provides responses based on their personal experiences, insights, and perceptions.

In conducting the interview, the researchers will take written notes of the respondents’ answers. With the consent of the participants, smartphones will also be used as audio recording devices to ensure accurate documentation of responses and to prevent misinterpretation of data. All recordings and written notes will remain confidential and will be used strictly for academic purposes. The identities of the participants will not be disclosed to protect their privacy.

The researchers will utilize an interview protocol to guide the flow of conversation. The interview protocol serves as an instrument of inquiry that contains prepared questions aligned with the objectives of the study. It ensures that the discussion remains focused on understanding how residents of Barangay 175 perceive the effects of sustainable development initiatives implemented in their community.

Validity of the Research Instrument

To ensure the validity of the research instrument, the interview guide was developed based on the statement of the problem and objectives of the study, and supported by relevant concepts related to sustainable development, good governance, and social responsibility. The interview questions were designed to directly elicit the perceptions and experiences of residents of Barangay 175 regarding the effects of sustainable development projects in their community.

Prior to the conduct of the actual interviews, the interview questions were reviewed for clarity, relevance, and alignment with the research objectives. The questions were structured to ensure that they were understandable to the participants and capable of generating meaningful and in-depth responses. Necessary revisions were made to improve the flow and appropriateness of the questions based on feedback and evaluation.

This process established the content validity of the research instrument, ensuring that the interview guide adequately represented the key concepts being explored and was suitable for gathering reliable qualitative data to address the objectives of the study.

Data Gathering Procedure

This study will utilize a qualitative research design to gather in-depth information from selected participants. The primary method of data collection will be face-to-face interviews conducted within Barangay 175.

A total of ten (10) respondents will be purposively selected from the community to ensure that the participants will possess relevant knowledge and experiences related to the research topic. The researchers will prepare a structured interview guide consisting of open-ended questions to allow respondents to freely express their thoughts and experiences. Each interview will be conducted individually in a quiet and comfortable location within Barangay 175 to ensure confidentiality and minimize distractions.

During the interview, responses will be carefully recorded through note-taking and, when permitted, audio recording. The researchers will ensure that ethical standards such as voluntary participation, confidentiality, and anonymity of the respondents will be strictly observed throughout the data gathering process.

After all interviews are completed, the collected data will be transcribed and organized for analysis to identify common themes and patterns relevant to the study.

Statistical Treatment of Data

Since this study employs a qualitative research design, the data gathered through in-depth interviews will be analyzed using thematic analysis. This method is appropriate because the research aims to explore and understand the perceptions, lived experiences, and insights of the residents of Barangay 175 regarding the effects of sustainable development projects implemented by the Local Government Units (LGUs).

All interviews will be audio-recorded (with consent) and transcribed verbatim to ensure accuracy. The researchers will carefully read and review the transcripts multiple times to become familiar with the data. Significant statements and meaningful responses related to project implementation, governance, sustainability, trust, and community impact will be identified and coded.

After coding, related ideas will be grouped into broader themes that reflect common patterns in the participants' responses. These themes may include perceived benefits, implementation challenges, gaps between policy intentions and lived

experiences, issues of transparency and accountability, community trust, and recommendations for improvement.

The identified themes will then be interpreted and discussed in relation to the research questions and the principles of good governance and social responsibility. To ensure credibility and trustworthiness, the researchers may conduct member checking by allowing selected participants to review the summarized interpretations of their responses.

The findings will be presented in narrative form, supported by selected verbatim quotations from participants to accurately reflect their voices and experiences.

Chapter 4

PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS, AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

INTRODUCTION

This chapter presents, analyzes, and interprets the data gathered from the in-depth interviews conducted with ten (10) selected residents of Barangay 175. Using thematic analysis, recurring patterns and themes were identified from the participants' responses and organized according to the research questions of the study. The findings highlight the residents' perceptions of sustainable development projects and reveal emerging gaps between intended objectives and actual community experiences

Data Analysis

This section presents the analysis of the data gathered from the respondents of the study. The collected information was organized and examined to identify patterns and relevant insights related to the research objectives. The results of the analysis serve as the basis for understanding the findings of the study.

Respondent 1

1. PERCEPTION OF LGU SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT PROJECTS

1.1 What Sustainable Development Projects are you aware of in Barangay 175?

The first respondent mentioned educational assistance programs as the sustainable development initiative they are aware of in the barangay. The respondent stated, *“Education, Scholarship.”* This indicates that educational support is one of the visible programs recognized by some residents in Barangay 175.

1.2. In your opinion, do these projects address the real needs of the community? Why or why not?

The first respondent expressed that these projects address the needs of the community based on information seen online. The respondent stated, *“Yes, nakikita ko naman via social media.”* This suggests that the respondent perceives the programs as beneficial, although their awareness may primarily come from social media updates rather than direct personal experience with the projects.

2. RESIDENTS’ EXPERIENCE WITH IMPLEMENTATION AND SUSTAINABILITY

2.1 Can you describe your personal experience with the implementation of these projects?

The respondent shared that they did not personally experience inconsistencies but observed benefits received by family members. The respondent stated, *“Sa side ko, wala namang inconsistent. Sa mga kapatid ko kasi nabibigyan sila ng financial support ng Barangay 175.”* This suggests that while the respondent is not a direct beneficiary, their household has experienced the benefits of barangay financial assistance, indicating that such programs reach some families within the community.

2.2 What challenges have you personally experienced in relation to these projects?

The respondent mentioned that accessing the programs involves certain requirements. The respondent stated, “*Requirements.*” This indicates that documentation or eligibility requirements may act as a minor barrier for residents seeking assistance.

3. IMPACT OF INCONSISTENT EXECUTION

3.1. Have you observed any projects that were delayed, discontinued, or inconsistently implemented? Please describe.

The response of the first respondent indicates that they are not aware of any sustainable development projects implemented in the barangay. The respondent directly stated, “Wala naman.” This suggests a lack of visibility or awareness of barangay initiatives from the perspective of this resident.

3.2. In what ways did unfinished or delayed projects affect the overall condition of the community?

The first respondent stated that unfinished or delayed projects do not have any noticeable effect on the community, as expressed in the response, “Wala.” This indicates that the respondent may not have directly experienced the impact of delayed projects.

4. OBSTACLES AND TRANSPARENCY ISSUES

4.1 What do you think are the main obstacles preventing the successful implementation of these projects?

The first respondent believes that financial limitations may affect the success of barangay projects. The participant stated, “Siguro lack of funds.” This response suggests that the resident perceives insufficient funding as a major barrier to project implementation. It indicates that the respondent may feel that projects cannot be completed properly because the available resources are not enough to sustain them.

4.2. In your view, does transparency play a role in project gaps? Please explain.

The first respondent believes that transparency is present in the barangay to some extent. The participant stated, “Yes, and dito may transparency, nandyan may bulletin board sila sa loob ng barangay.” This response suggests that the resident recognizes the efforts of the barangay to provide information to the public through visible channels such as bulletin boards. The presence of these posted announcements may give the impression that the barangay is attempting to inform residents about projects, activities, or financial matters. However, while the respondent acknowledges the existence of transparency mechanisms, the statement mainly reflects that transparency is observed through publicly displayed information rather than through deeper engagement or detailed explanation of project implementation.

5. EFFECTS ON TRUST AND GOVERNANCE PERCEPTION

5.1. How have these development projects affected your trust in the local government?

The response of the first respondent indicates that development projects contribute positively to the respondent’s level of trust in the local government. The respondent perceives that the presence of projects reflects the effort of the barangay officials to improve the community. This positive perception was expressed when the respondent stated that “mas nagiging trusted sa mga projects.” This implies that visible

improvements and implemented programs can strengthen residents confidence in the government and encourage a more favorable view of local leadership.

5.2. How do these experiences shape your overall perception of governance in Barangay 175?

The First respondent stated that they regularly witness the implementation of development projects, partly due to their personal connection with a barangay staff member. This exposure allows the respondent to observe improvements in the community, which positively shapes their perception of governance. Direct observation of projects may increase transparency and influence residents to develop a more favorable evaluation of local leadership.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT

6.1. What improvements would you recommend for future Sustainable Development Projects?

The response, “*pabahay... kasi marami dito... nangungupahan,*” suggests a concern for housing insecurity within the barangay. This indicates that many residents do not have permanent homes, implying that future development projects should prioritize affordable housing programs to ensure long-term residential stability.

6.2. If you were given the opportunity, what project would you prioritize for Barangay 175 and why?

The response, “*pabahay and livelihood training,*” reflects a dual concern for both shelter and economic stability. By pairing housing with livelihood training, the respondent implies that providing homes alone is not sufficient; residents must also be equipped with skills to sustain their daily needs. This suggests an understanding that

sustainable development should address both basic needs and income-generating opportunities, promoting long-term self-sufficiency.

Respondent 2

1. PERCEPTION OF LGU SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT PROJECTS

1.1 What Sustainable Development Projects are you aware of in Barangay 175?

The second respondent expressed that they are not aware of any sustainable development projects implemented in the barangay. The respondent stated, "*Wala, wala akong nararamdaman.*" This response indicates a lack of awareness or visibility of barangay initiatives from the perspective of this resident.

1.2. In your opinion, do these projects address the real needs of the community? Why or why not?

The second respondent stated that the projects do not address the needs of the community because they are not aware of any initiatives being implemented. The respondent explained, "*Wala, kasi wala nga kasi.*" This response suggests that the absence of visible programs leads to the perception that community needs are not being addressed by the barangay.

2. RESIDENTS' EXPERIENCE WITH IMPLEMENTATION AND SUSTAINABILITY

2.1 Can you describe your personal experience with the implementation of these projects?

The respondent expressed that they have not personally felt the presence of barangay programs. The respondent stated, "*Di ko nga alam bakit ganun, wala akong nararamdaman sa kanila eh. Nakakuha ako financial solo parent pero sa DSWD.*" This

response suggests that the respondent's experience with assistance came from a national agency rather than the barangay, indicating limited perceived visibility or impact of barangay-led initiatives.

2.2 What challenges have you personally experienced in relation to these projects?

The respondent shared disappointment regarding the lack of response to requests. The respondent stated, *"Walang experience. Wala na akong pag-asa sa kanila, minsan nag-request ako diyan, wala talaga."* This reflects a sense of dissatisfaction and perceived lack of responsiveness from the barangay, which may affect residents' trust in local governance.

3. IMPACT OF INCONSISTENT EXECUTION

3.1. Have you observed any projects that were delayed, discontinued, or inconsistently implemented? Please describe.

The second respondent expressed that they have not observed any projects because they rarely see the barangay leadership. The respondent stated, *"Wala, kasi hindi ko naman nakikita si Cap eh."* The respondent also questioned the role of the Sangguniang Kabataan by saying, *"Ay SK hindi ko maramdaman yan, bakit may SK pa eh wala naman ginagawa dito."* This indicates dissatisfaction and a perception that youth leadership initiatives are not visible in the community.

3.2. In what ways did unfinished or delayed projects affect the overall condition of the community?

The second respondent also stated that there was no noticeable impact, saying, *"Wala din, kase wala naman akong pakielam sa kanila eh."* However, the respondent acknowledged that projects could potentially influence the community by stating, *"Pero kung meron silang ginawa, pwede maka apekto yon sa community at pwede din hindi*

rin makatulong kase wala nga eh.” This suggests a sense of indifference while recognizing the possible importance of community development projects.

4. OBSTACLES AND TRANSPARENCY ISSUES

4.1 What do you think are the main obstacles preventing the successful implementation of these projects?

The second respondent expressed concern about unfair distribution of opportunities and benefits within the barangay. The participant stated, “Dito pag may kakilala ka sa barangay yun lang yung nabibigyan nila... kapag malapit ka sa kusina, makikinabang ka.” This statement reflects the resident’s perception that favoritism or personal connections influence who receives assistance or benefits. It suggests a feeling that the system may not be entirely fair to all residents.

4.2. In your view, does transparency play a role in project gaps? Please explain.

The second respondent believed that transparency is very important, especially in showing how public funds are used. The participant stated, “Yan ang importante sa ngayon, kailangan transparent kung saan ginagamit ang pera”. This response highlights the belief that openness and accountability are necessary to build trust between officials and residents.

5. EFFECTS ON TRUST AND GOVERNANCE PERCEPTION

5.1. How have these development projects affected your trust in the local government?

The second respondent demonstrates strong dissatisfaction with the current leadership of the barangay, which significantly affects their level of trust in the local government. The response suggests that the respondent believes governance can

improve if new officials are given the opportunity to lead. This sentiment is reflected when the respondent mentioned that “wala nang tiwala, ang gusto ko lang mapalitan yung mga nakaupo sa barangay para may pagbabago.” The statement indicates that negative experiences with development projects or governance practices may lead residents to desire leadership change.

5.2. How do these experiences shape your overall perception of governance in Barangay 175?

The second respondent described their perception of governance as “boring,” which may indicate a lack of engagement or interest in barangay activities. This response suggests that the respondent may not perceive significant initiatives or impactful programs that influence their daily life. Such perceptions may arise when government actions are not visible or do not effectively reach certain members of the community.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT

6.1. What improvements would you recommend for future Sustainable Development Projects?

The statement, “*gusto ko lang... yung curfew,*” reflects a desire for stricter policy implementation related to community discipline. This implies that the respondent associates curfew enforcement with improved safety and order in the barangay.

6.2. If you were given the opportunity, what project would you prioritize for Barangay 175 and why?

The statement, “*sa mga bata (curfew),*” highlights a focus on youth regulation and protection. The respondent specifically targets children, implying concerns about their safety, behavior, or exposure to risks during late hours. This suggests that

implementing curfew is seen as a preventive measure that can guide the younger population and contribute to overall community discipline and security

Respondent 3

1. PERCEPTION OF LGU SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT PROJECTS

1.1 What Sustainable Development Projects are you aware of in Barangay 175?

The third respondent mentioned environmental and educational assistance programs implemented in the barangay. The respondent stated, *“Ang alam ko lang naglilinis sila every Friday, Saturday tungkol sa kalinisan, 5k once a year educational assistance.”* This indicates that clean-up initiatives and financial assistance for students are among the programs recognized by some residents.

1.2. In your opinion, do these projects address the real needs of the community? Why or why not?

The third respondent expressed that these programs do not fully address the needs of the community. The respondent stated, *“Hindi, ang nakatira sa Brgy. 175 hindi ramdam ng tao, hindi lahat nakaka-avail mga ginagawa na programa.”* This response suggests that although programs exist, their benefits may not reach all residents equally.

2. RESIDENTS’ EXPERIENCE WITH IMPLEMENTATION AND SUSTAINABILITY

2.1 Can you describe your personal experience with the implementation of these projects?

The respondent highlighted the importance of educational financial assistance. The respondent stated, *“Malaking bagay. Malaking bagay yung 5k sa student lalo na sa mga kabataan na naghihikahos. Oo magagamit sa expenses. Hindi sa sapat, 5k lang yun eh. Eh dalawang sem lang tayo sa isang taon. Dapat twice.”* This response indicates that financial assistance programs are valued by residents, particularly students from financially struggling families, although the amount provided may not be sufficient for long-term educational needs.

2.2 What challenges have you personally experienced in relation to these projects?

The respondent observed that many visible projects come from the city government rather than the barangay. The respondent stated, *“Hindi ko talaga ramdam project ng barangay... kalimitan kasi puro city yan eh... Financial assistance lang yung alam ko.”* This suggests that barangay initiatives may be less visible compared to city-led programs, affecting residents’ perception of local project implementation.

3. IMPACT OF INCONSISTENT EXECUTION

3.1. Have you observed any projects that were delayed, discontinued, or inconsistently implemented? Please describe.

The third respondent explained that they could not identify any specific barangay projects and believed that most visible programs come from higher levels of government. The respondent stated, *“Hindi ko masabi kung project ng barangay, kase kung pagbabasihan naten ang project ng barangay, wala akong nakikita kase ang kalimitan na binababa is galing National, kung hindi National galing sa City.”* This response reflects the perception that sustainable development initiatives may not originate from the barangay but from national or city authorities.

3.2. In what ways did unfinished or delayed projects affect the overall condition of the community

The third respondent mentioned issues related to waste management in the community. The respondent stated, “Sa basura na yan, meron na silang truck dati dito kaso hindi naman nag f function.” This indicates that previous resources intended to address waste management are no longer functioning, which may contribute to sanitation problems in the area.

4. OBSTACLES AND TRANSPARENCY ISSUES

4.1 What do you think are the main obstacles preventing the successful implementation of these projects?

The Third respondent pointed out that the issue may be related to leadership rather than resources. The participant explained, “Sa leadership kasi nandyan naman yung budget, nandyan naman lahat. Wala paring implementation.” This response indicates that the resident believes that even if resources are available, ineffective leadership or poor management may still prevent projects from being implemented successfully.

4.2. In your view, does transparency play a role in project gaps? Please explain.

The third respondent acknowledged that some information is displayed publicly but questioned its actual impact. The participant shared, “May transparency... nakita niyo yung bulletin board doon... pero in actual nandon ba?” This response suggests that although information is presented, the resident feels that the results of the projects may not be fully experienced by the community.

5. EFFECTS ON TRUST AND GOVERNANCE PERCEPTION

5.1. How have these development projects affected your trust in the local government?

The third respondent reflects a clear loss of confidence in the barangay leadership. The respondent's statement suggests that the implemented projects or governance practices have not met their expectations, resulting in diminished trust toward the local government. This feeling of distrust is directly expressed in the respondent's statement, "wala na akong trust." Such responses highlight how dissatisfaction with government performance can weaken the relationship between the community and local leaders.

5.2. How do these experiences shape your overall perception of governance in Barangay 175?

The third respondent rated the governance of Barangay 175 at 50 out of 100, reflecting a neutral or moderate perception. This evaluation indicates that the respondent acknowledges both positive and negative aspects of governance. The rating suggests that while some initiatives may exist, they may not be sufficient to fully satisfy the expectations of residents.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT

6.1. What improvements would you recommend for future Sustainable Development Projects?

The participant's suggestion, "*educational assistance, taasan nila... sa college dapat... twice yan,*" highlights the need to strengthen educational support. This indicates that residents view education as a crucial investment for long-term development and improved opportunities.

6.2. If you were given the opportunity, what project would you prioritize for Barangay 175 and why?

The response, "*peace and order, lawakan... gawing accessible lahat ng covered court,*" combines concerns about safety and inclusivity in public spaces. The suggestion

to expand peace and order efforts indicates a perceived need for stronger enforcement, while making covered courts accessible suggests a desire for shared community spaces. This implies that development should foster both security and social inclusion, allowing residents to safely engage in communal activities

Respondent 4

1. PERCEPTION OF LGU SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT PROJECTS

1.1 What Sustainable Development Projects are you aware of in Barangay 175?

The fourth respondent stated that they are not aware of many projects in the barangay and only mentioned assistance programs. The respondent said, *“Wala, ayuda. Yun lang alam ko.”* This response indicates limited awareness of development initiatives within the community.

1.2. In your opinion, do these projects address the real needs of the community? Why or why not?

The fourth respondent believes that the projects only partially address the needs of the community. The respondent stated, *“Slight lang siguro... hindi nakaka-abot. Hindi effective, hindi equal sa pagbibigay.”* This suggests that the respondent perceives the programs as unevenly distributed and not entirely effective in addressing community needs.

2. RESIDENTS’ EXPERIENCE WITH IMPLEMENTATION AND SUSTAINABILITY

2.1 Can you describe your personal experience with the implementation of these projects?

The respondent shared that they are more aware of programs initiated by the SK or the city rather than the barangay. The respondent stated, *“Wala, buti pa nga ang SK ng barangay naanohan namin kaysa sa mismong barangay... Kay mayor ang ayuda... Naririnig ko yung nakakahingi sa barangay yung sa abuloy.”* This indicates that barangay projects may not be widely recognized by residents, while other government units appear more visible in delivering services.

2.2 What challenges have you personally experienced in relation to these projects?

The respondent suggested the need for better communication with residents. The respondent stated, *“Pagkakaroon ng pagbabago, meron dapat siyang forum ba... In terms of requirements, maayos naman siya.”* This suggests that while administrative processes appear efficient, information dissemination and community engagement may need improvement.

3. IMPACT OF INCONSISTENT EXECUTION

3.1. Have you observed any projects that were delayed, discontinued, or inconsistently implemented? Please describe.

The fourth respondent mentioned a drainage or canal project but clarified that it was managed by the national government. The respondent stated, *“Ang nagawa lang na nakita ko is itong sa kanal, eh National naman ang may hawak niyan eh.”* However, the respondent also acknowledged that the barangay captain shows support for school-related programs, stating, *“Very supportive naman si cap sa mga teachers sa elementary school kapag may program.”* This suggests that while large projects may not be attributed to the barangay, the leadership is still involved in supporting community activities.

3.2. In what ways did unfinished or delayed projects affect the overall condition of the community

The fourth respondent expressed disappointment regarding the lack of streetlight implementation in the community. The respondent stated, “Nag expect kami na magkaroon ng implementation sa street light eh kaso wala.” The respondent also mentioned that some projects may exist but are not visible to residents, stating, “Meron man kaya lang hindi naman namin nakikita, kase ang katwiran nila is malapit kame sa isang politician.” Additionally, the respondent described limited interaction with the barangay office, saying, “Nakakapunta lang kame sa barangay kapag kukuha ng papel.” These responses suggest unmet expectations and limited engagement between residents and local governance.

4. OBSTACLES AND TRANSPARENCY ISSUES

4.1 What do you think are the main obstacles preventing the successful implementation of these projects?

The fourth respondent strongly associated the failure of projects with corruption. The participant stated, “Corruption, yun ang number one... kasi magkukulang ang pondo kapag ganon... putol putol yung pag implement.” This suggests that the resident perceives corruption as a factor that reduces the budget allocated for projects. As a result, the respondent believes that projects become incomplete or poorly implemented.

4.2 In your view, does transparency play a role in project gaps? Please explain.

The fourth respondent believes transparency plays an important role in governance. The participant stated, “Oo importante yan, para alam ng mga nasasakupan yung kilos sa loob ng barangay.” This suggests that the resident feels transparency allows community members to stay informed about the actions and decisions of barangay officials.

5. EFFECTS ON TRUST AND GOVERNANCE PERCEPTION

5.1. How have these development projects affected your trust in the local government?

The fourth respondent expresses a sense of neglect and disconnection from the local government. The perception that residents are being overlooked in government programs contributes to their declining interest and trust in barangay governance. This feeling is evident when the respondent explained that “parang wala na nga kaming pakielam... ultimo maliit na bagay tulad ng ayuda nilalagpasan kami.” The statement suggests that perceived unfairness in the distribution of assistance can lead residents to feel excluded, which ultimately affects their trust in the government.

5.2. How do these experiences shape your overall perception of governance in Barangay 175?

The fourth respondent reflects dissatisfaction with the current governance practices in the barangay. The respondent believes that the leadership and systems currently in place require significant improvements to better serve the community. This viewpoint is expressed when the respondent mentioned that “kailangan ng malaking pagbabago.” The statement indicates a desire for reforms that can address existing governance issues.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT

6.1. What improvements would you recommend for future Sustainable Development Projects?

The response, “*peace and order... at garbage collection,*” emphasizes the importance of both social stability and environmental cleanliness. This suggests that the respondent perceives these two aspects as interconnected factors in achieving a well-functioning community.

6.2. If you were given the opportunity, what project would you prioritize for Barangay 175 and why?

The statement, *“ayusin ang peace and order,”* emphasizes the need to improve community safety and discipline. The straightforward nature of the response suggests that issues related to peace and order are both evident and pressing. This indicates that the respondent views social stability as a foundational element of any successful development initiative.

Respondent 5

1. PERCEPTION OF LGU SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT PROJECTS

1.1 What Sustainable Development Projects are you aware of in Barangay 175?

The fifth respondent stated that they are not aware of many projects implemented by the barangay but mentioned activities conducted by the Sangguniang Kabataan. The respondent stated, *“Barangay? Wala masyado... more on SK meron seminar nakakatulong HIV awareness seminar.”* This indicates that youth-led initiatives may be more visible to some residents compared to barangay programs.

1.2. In your opinion, do these projects address the real needs of the community? Why or why not?

The fifth respondent simply answered, *“Hindi.”* This response reflects the perception that the existing programs are not sufficient to meet the needs of the community.

2. RESIDENTS’ EXPERIENCE WITH IMPLEMENTATION AND SUSTAINABILITY

2.1 Can you describe your personal experience with the implementation of these projects?

The respondent stated that they have not personally felt the impact of barangay projects. The respondent said, *“Parang wala kasi akong nararamdaman na projects... parang di lahat nakakatanggap ng ganun.”* This indicates a perception that barangay initiatives may not reach all residents equally, leading to limited awareness or involvement.

2.2 What challenges have you personally experienced in relation to these projects?

The respondent reported minimal challenges. The respondent stated, *“Wala naman masyado.”* This may suggest limited interaction with barangay services or a lack of direct engagement with the programs.

3. IMPACT OF INCONSISTENT EXECUTION

3.1. Have you observed any projects that were delayed, discontinued, or inconsistently implemented? Please describe.

The fifth respondent identified educational assistance as a program provided in the barangay but noted that it is sometimes rescheduled. The respondent stated, *“Sa may educational assistance namen, na kahit naturuloy siya is may times na nire re-schedule.”* The respondent also raised concerns about the health center, saying, *“May nakikita din akong Health Center, pero walang mga tao so anong silbi non?”* This indicates that while services may exist, their implementation and accessibility may be inconsistent.

3.2. In what ways did unfinished or delayed projects affect the overall condition of the community

The fifth respondent highlighted the difficulties experienced by residents when infrastructure problems remain unresolved. The respondent stated, “Madaming tao ang nahihirapan kapag hindi naayos yung lugar nila.” The respondent also described flooding problems in specific areas by stating, “Sa may Matarik o Robes, binabaha sila kapag malakas yung ulan, so throughout that day ang iisipin nila is kung papaano sila makakalikas.” This response indicates that delays in addressing infrastructure issues may pose safety risks to residents.

4. OBSTACLES AND TRANSPARENCY ISSUES

4.1 What do you think are the main obstacles preventing the successful implementation of these projects?

The fifth respondent also emphasized corruption as a major issue in project implementation. The participant stated, “Yung una is corruption... napapansin ko syempre ang laki ng lugar natin so syempre malaki rin yung budget dyaan.” This response suggests that the resident believes that despite the barangay having a large budget due to its size, corruption may prevent the proper use of these funds for community development.

4.2. In your view, does transparency play a role in project gaps? Please explain.

The fifth respondent expressed uncertainty about transparency through an example of leadership absence. The participant stated, “Sa tingin ko wala... nagkaroon sila ng inauguration pero wala yung kapitan.” This response indicates that the resident may question the openness and accountability of the leadership based on their observations.

5. EFFECTS ON TRUST AND GOVERNANCE PERCEPTION

5.1. How have these development projects affected your trust in the local government?

The fifth respondent highlights that the respondent's trust in the local government is influenced by the consistency and quality of development projects. The respondent recognizes that effective governance can build trust, while inconsistency in delivering projects can gradually reduce public confidence. This idea was emphasized when the respondent stated that "kung maganda yung naibigay sa inyo may trust ka sa kanila... pero once nawala yung consistency nila sa projects, unti-unting nababawasan ang tiwala." This suggests that sustained and reliable project implementation is essential for maintaining residents' trust.

5.2. How do these experiences shape your overall perception of governance in Barangay 175?

The perception of the fifth respondent in governance is heavily influenced by their personal experience during their on-the-job training in the barangay. Witnessing what they perceived as corruption in the distribution of rice assistance led them to develop a negative perception of governance. This response highlights how direct exposure to government processes can shape individuals' views about transparency and fairness in public service.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT

6.1. What improvements would you recommend for future Sustainable Development Projects?

The statement, "*unahin ang... binabahang lugar (flood control)... ayuda... dapat natatanggap... at sapat,*" reflects concerns about both environmental vulnerability and governance. This implies that residents prioritize disaster mitigation while also expecting fair and sufficient distribution of assistance.

6.2. If you were given the opportunity, what project would you prioritize for Barangay 175 and why?

The response, “*gumawa ng health care (center)... makakapagbigay agad ng mga gamot,*” reflects concern for accessible and responsive healthcare services. The emphasis on immediate provision of medicine suggests gaps in current health infrastructure and delays in accessing care. This implies that residents prioritize health security and service accessibility, especially in times of urgent need.

Respondent 6

1. PERCEPTION OF LGU SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT PROJECTS

1.1 What Sustainable Development Projects are you aware of in Barangay 175?

The sixth respondent identified several programs related to environmental management and healthcare services. The respondent mentioned “*Clean-up drive, kalinisan program every week or month, healthcare free check-ups, pagpapatayo health centers.*” This suggests that some residents are aware of multiple initiatives intended to improve environmental sanitation and public health in the barangay.

1.2. In your opinion, do these projects address the real needs of the community? Why or why not?

The sixth respondent expressed a conditional view regarding the effectiveness of these programs. The respondent stated, “*Maybe at some point natutugunan siya... sana nga nagagawa.. hindi lang puro social media posting.*” This indicates that while the respondent acknowledges the potential benefits of these initiatives, there is also concern about whether the programs are consistently implemented beyond public announcements.

2. RESIDENTS' EXPERIENCE WITH IMPLEMENTATION AND SUSTAINABILITY

2.1 Can you describe your personal experience with the implementation of these projects?

The respondent explained that they are more involved in SK activities than barangay programs. The respondent stated, *“Di kasi talaga ako active sa mga barangay programs, more on sa SK ako active... feel ko may kulang... hindi lang sa certain area.”* This suggests that youth-led initiatives may appear more active or visible compared to some barangay programs.

2.2 What challenges have you personally experienced in relation to these projects?

The respondent raised concerns about unequal distribution of assistance. The respondent stated, *“Di lahat ng resident ay natatap... kung sino mas may kapit sila ang nakakatanggap.”* This indicates a perception of favoritism or unequal access to resources, which may affect residents' confidence in program fairness.

3. IMPACT OF INCONSISTENT EXECUTION

3.1. Have you observed any projects that were delayed, discontinued, or inconsistently implemented? Please describe.

The sixth respondent mentioned a river-cleaning initiative that was implemented but not sustained. The respondent stated, *“Every friday pumupunta sila Palmera para maglinis ilog pero hindi nila napagpatuloy.”* The respondent also described the environmental impact by saying, *“Kapag makikita mo sobrang dumi, kapag dadaan ka doon sobrang baho, so paano na lang yung mga dumadaan don.”* The respondent further emphasized the responsibility of leaders in maintaining community safety and image, stating, *“Siyempre dapat ma maintain nila yung protection or safety ng mga tao na nakatira dito sa barangay at kung sino man yung bibisita dito.”* Additionally, the

respondent noted, “Kailangan din natin i maintain yung image, ikaw as politician is nagre reflect yung characteristics mo or kung gaano ka ka-good leader doon san ipinapakita or maipapakita mo sa kaayusan ng community.” These statements reflect the respondent’s expectation for consistent environmental management and responsible leadership.

3.2. In what ways did unfinished or delayed projects affect the overall condition of the community

The sixth respondent emphasized the environmental risks associated with poor sanitation. The respondent stated, “Sobrang risky ng ganon eh, makita mo madumi yung kapaligiran mo tapos mabaho is parang mawawalan siguro sila ng gana.” The respondent also encouraged community awareness and responsibility by stating, “I just hope na makakapag reflect yung mga tao sa nakikita nila hindi yung patuloy na magbubulag-bulagan sila.” This response highlights concerns regarding environmental health and community accountability.

4. OBSTACLES AND TRANSPARENCY ISSUES

4.1 What do you think are the main obstacles preventing the successful implementation of these projects?

The sixth respondent believes that the responsibility lies mainly with barangay officials. The participant shared, “Sila mismo, yung officials mismo... sila yung pipirma, sila yung makakapag implement pero they choose not to.” This response indicates that the resident feels that local officials have the authority and ability to implement programs but may lack the willingness or commitment to do so.

4.2. In your view, does transparency play a role in project gaps? Please explain.

The sixth respondent acknowledged the importance of transparency but expressed skepticism about its practice. The participant stated, “Yes, pero dito wala namang

transparency... wala kang makikitang sobrang transparent sa fundings.” This suggests that the resident feels that financial information may not be fully disclosed to the public.

5. EFFECTS ON TRUST AND GOVERNANCE PERCEPTION

5.1. How have these development projects affected your trust in the local government?

The sixth respondent demonstrates a high level of awareness regarding leadership and governance practices. Because of this awareness, the respondent evaluates the performance of the local government more critically. The negative perception toward development projects is reflected in the respondent’s statement that “sobrang nakakaapekto siya sa kinabibilangang lokal na pamumuno... kasi hindi ako student na walang pakialam sa nangyayari sa pamumuno.” This indicates that individuals who actively observe and analyze governance processes tend to form stronger opinions regarding leadership effectiveness.

5.2. How do these experiences shape your overall perception of governance in Barangay 175?

The sixth respondent evaluates barangay governance based on their background and experience as a student leader. Because of their leadership experience, the respondent has developed higher expectations regarding how leaders should perform their responsibilities. This perspective is expressed when the respondent stated that “lumaki ako bilang student leader kaya mataas yung standard ko sa pamumuno.” This indicates that individuals with leadership experience often analyze governance more critically.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT

6.1. What improvements would you recommend for future Sustainable Development Projects?

The statement, *“be consistent to their own projects,”* reflects a concern about the continuity and reliability of development initiatives. The brevity of the response suggests a straightforward but significant issue—projects may be started but not sustained or completed effectively. This implies past experiences of inconsistency, which can lead to diminished trust in local programs. The respondent is therefore emphasizing the importance of sustainability through consistency, where development efforts must be maintained over time to produce meaningful impact.

6.2. If you were given the opportunity, what project would you prioritize for Barangay 175 and why?

The statement, *“informal labors... registration process and designated spaces,”* highlights the need to support informal workers such as street vendors. The respondent proposes formalizing their activities through registration and proper allocation of spaces. This suggests an awareness of the economic role of informal labor and the need for inclusive economic policies that both regulate and protect their livelihoods.

Respondent 7

1. PERCEPTION OF LGU SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT PROJECTS

1.1 What Sustainable Development Projects are you aware of in Barangay 175?

The seventh respondent stated that they have not observed many barangay projects, although a road project was mentioned. The respondent stated, *“Wala akong nakikitang projects, may nagawa about kalsada pero 10 years bago nagawa.”* This

suggests that infrastructure improvements may occur but are perceived as taking a long time before completion.

1.2. In your opinion, do these projects address the real needs of the community? Why or why not?

The seventh respondent acknowledged that some projects may address community needs, particularly infrastructure improvements. The respondent stated, *“Siguro sa project na yun about sa kalsada, yes.”* This indicates that specific projects may still be viewed positively by some residents.

2. RESIDENTS’ EXPERIENCE WITH IMPLEMENTATION AND SUSTAINABILITY

2.1 Can you describe your personal experience with the implementation of these projects?

The respondent referred to infrastructure projects and delays in completion. The respondent stated, *“Siguro yung mga buildings na ginagawa ngayon... lalo na yung multipurpose hall, nauurong nang nauurong.”* This suggests that construction projects are visible in the community but may face scheduling or implementation delays.

2.2 What challenges have you personally experienced in relation to these projects?

The respondent mentioned disturbances caused by construction activities. The respondent stated, *“Siguro yung ingay kasi tuwing gabi, malapit sa bahay namin... super ingay.”* This indicates that infrastructure development may temporarily disrupt residents’ daily routines.

3. IMPACT OF INCONSISTENT EXECUTION

3.1. Have you observed any projects that were delayed, discontinued, or inconsistently implemented? Please describe.

The seventh respondent referred to the construction of a multipurpose hall as a project in the barangay but indicated that its progress has been delayed. The respondent stated, “Yung regarding sa Multi purpose Hall na umuurong yung paggawa, pero alam ko dapat this year siya matatapos.” This response suggests that infrastructure projects exist but may not progress as expected.

3.2. In what ways did unfinished or delayed projects affect the overall condition of the community

The seventh respondent described disturbances caused by ongoing construction activities. The respondent stated, “Maingay siya tuwing gabi or every time na may ginagawa sila, so ang nangyayari sa mga tao is hindi sila makatulog agad.” This indicates that unfinished infrastructure projects can affect residents’ comfort and daily routines.

4. OBSTACLES AND TRANSPARENCY ISSUES

4.1 What do you think are the main obstacles preventing the successful implementation of these projects?

The seventh respondent also identified corruption as a common and persistent issue. The participant stated, “Corruption, di na yan mawawala.” This response reflects a strong perception that corruption is deeply rooted in governance and is a recurring problem that affects the success of community projects.

4.2. In your view, does transparency play a role in project gaps? Please explain.

The seventh respondent strongly emphasized the value of transparency. The participant stated, “Kung transparent sila malalaman ng bawat tao kung tugma ba yung

nagastos nila sa project.” This indicates that transparency is seen as a way for residents to verify whether public funds are used appropriately.

5. EFFECTS ON TRUST AND GOVERNANCE PERCEPTION

5.1. How have these development projects affected your trust in the local government?

The seventh respondent has concern for the welfare of the residents who should be receiving services from the local government. The respondent believes that certain members of the community may not be receiving the proper assistance they deserve. This concern is highlighted in the statement “kawawa yung mga tao na dapat pagserbisyuhan.” Such perceptions suggest that when residents believe that services are not fairly or effectively delivered, it can negatively affect their trust in the barangay leadership.

5.2. How do these experiences shape your overall perception of governance in Barangay 175?

The response of the seventh respondent indicates dissatisfaction with the leadership of the barangay captain. The respondent believes that there are noticeable gaps in governance that affect the effectiveness of leadership within the community. This concern is reflected when the respondent stated that “hindi ko gusto ang pamamahala ng ating kapitan dahil sa gaps sa pamamahala.” This suggests that leadership performance is a key factor in shaping residents’ perception of governance.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT

6.1. What improvements would you recommend for future Sustainable Development Projects?

The response, *“transparency... mas maagap na pagpapagawa... at mas maayos na governance,”* points to a comprehensive critique of governance practices. The emphasis on transparency suggests concerns about accountability and openness in decision-making processes. Meanwhile, the call for faster infrastructure development indicates frustration with delays or inefficiencies. Together, these highlight that residents see good governance—characterized by transparency, efficiency, and responsiveness—as essential to the success of development projects.

6.2. If you were given the opportunity, what project would you prioritize for Barangay 175 and why?

The response, *“inclusivity sa privileges para mas mafeel natin na included ang lahat,”* reflects a concern for equity and social inclusion. The use of “mafeel... included ang lahat” suggests that some members of the community may feel excluded from benefits or opportunities. This implies that development initiatives should ensure equal access to resources and services, fostering a sense of belonging among all residents.

Respondent 8

1. PERCEPTION OF LGU SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT PROJECTS

1.1 What Sustainable Development Projects are you aware of in Barangay 175?

The eighth respondent mentioned health and environmental programs as the projects they are aware of in the barangay. The respondent stated, *“Free medical check-ups weekly, may nabasa about clean-up drive.”* This suggests that healthcare services and environmental initiatives are among the programs recognized by residents.

1.2. In your opinion, do these projects address the real needs of the community? Why or why not?

The eighth respondent expressed that some projects do address community needs. The respondent stated, *“At some point yes, especially medical and clean-up.”* This response indicates that certain initiatives, particularly those related to health and sanitation, are considered beneficial for the community.

2. RESIDENTS’ EXPERIENCE WITH IMPLEMENTATION AND SUSTAINABILITY

2.1 Can you describe your personal experience with the implementation of these projects?

The respondent acknowledged that projects are implemented but noted limited coverage. The respondent stated, *“Well implemented ito pero limited yung mga nakakakuha ng mga service na to... di lahat ng 175 ay natutulungan.”* This suggests that while the respondent recognizes the efforts of the barangay, resource limitations may restrict the number of beneficiaries.

2.2 What challenges have you personally experienced in relation to these projects?

The respondent shared a personal experience related to limited health resources. The respondent stated, *“Lumapit ako sa barangay for anti rabies assistance pero wala silang resources... kulang sila sa kagamitan at gamot.”* This indicates that shortages in medical supplies and resources may affect the barangay’s ability to respond to residents’ needs.

3. IMPACT OF INCONSISTENT EXECUTION

3.1. Have you observed any projects that were delayed, discontinued, or inconsistently implemented? Please describe.

The eighth respondent emphasized problems related to road maintenance in the barangay. The respondent stated, “Maraming problema lalo na sa road here in 175, hindi agad naayos ng barangay although hindi sila ang main responsibility taker but meron padin silang i take na action.” This indicates that while the barangay may not be solely responsible for road infrastructure, residents still expect the local government to take action in addressing these concerns.

3.2. In what ways did unfinished or delayed projects affect the overall condition of the community

The eighth respondent explained that road construction and maintenance issues create transportation difficulties. The respondent stated, “Sa may Camarin to NHA area, medyo hassle yung pag travel around this area.” This suggests that delayed road improvements may affect mobility and accessibility within the community.

4. OBSTACLES AND TRANSPARENCY ISSUES

4.1 What do you think are the main obstacles preventing the successful implementation of these projects?

The eighth respondent emphasized the lack of coordination within the barangay. The participant stated, “Yung barangay itself is hindi masyadong coordinated... they lack people para maayos na mag flow yung mga project.” This response suggests that the resident believes that organizational issues, such as insufficient manpower and poor coordination, may affect the smooth implementation of projects.

4.2. In your view, does transparency play a role in project gaps? Please explain.

The eighth respondent provided a balanced perspective on the issue. The participant explained, “Yes and no... pinapakita nila but not all of it.” This response

suggests that the resident believes transparency exists to some degree, but not all information is fully disclosed to the public.

5. EFFECTS ON TRUST AND GOVERNANCE PERCEPTION

5.1. How have these development projects affected your trust in the local government?

The eighth respondent expressed dissatisfaction with the current condition of governance due to the presence of many unresolved issues within the community. The perception that there are still many problems that remain unaddressed contributes to the respondent's declining trust in the local government. This perspective is evident when the respondent stated that "medyo trashy ang perceptions and trust ko sa kanila kasi sobrang daming pwede pang gawin pero hindi naa-address." This indicates that residents evaluate the effectiveness of governance based on how well leaders address existing community concerns.

5.2. How do these experiences shape your overall perception of governance in Barangay 175?

The eighth respondent presents a moderately positive evaluation of governance, acknowledging that while there are some beneficial projects, there are still limitations in resources and implementation. This balanced perspective is reflected in the respondent's statement that "I would give it a rating of 6 or 7 out of 10... may good projects pero kulang pa sa resources." This suggests that residents may appreciate existing initiatives while still recognizing areas for improvement.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT

6.1. What improvements would you recommend for future Sustainable Development Projects?

The suggestion, *“kumuha ng mga sponsors para mapunan ang mga resources,”* reflects an awareness of limited government resources. This indicates that the respondent recognizes the need for alternative funding sources, such as private sector partnerships or external support. It shows a practical understanding that sustainable development is not solely dependent on local government but also on collaboration and resource mobilization, which can enhance the scope and continuity of projects

6.2. If you were given the opportunity, what project would you prioritize for Barangay 175 and why?

The statement, *“coordination for garbage collection,”* points to inefficiencies in current waste management systems. The focus on coordination suggests that the issue may not only be resources but also organization and communication. This implies that improving system management and coordination can significantly enhance service delivery in the barangay.

Respondent 9

1. PERCEPTION OF LGU SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT PROJECTS

1.1 What Sustainable Development Projects are you aware of in Barangay 175?

The ninth respondent mentioned environmental initiatives related to cleaning and creek improvement. The respondent stated, *“Yung mga nililinis at pinagawang creek.”* This suggests that environmental management projects are among the visible initiatives in the barangay.

1.2. In your opinion, do these projects address the real needs of the community? Why or why not?

The ninth respondent expressed that these projects do not fully solve the problems in the community. The respondent stated, *“Hindi kasi kahit ginawa na (creek) bumabaha parin.”* The respondent further suggested that proper waste management should be prioritized. This indicates that while infrastructure improvements may exist, other underlying issues still affect the community

2. RESIDENTS’ EXPERIENCE WITH IMPLEMENTATION AND SUSTAINABILITY

2.1 Can you describe your personal experience with the implementation of these projects?

The respondent observed routine community cleaning activities. The respondent stated, *“Parang okay naman, nakakalinis naman din sila kaso same process lang everyday. Linis sa umaga, nagkakat maghapon ang mga resident and repeat.”* This suggests that while sanitation efforts exist, sustaining cleanliness may remain challenging due to recurring waste disposal behaviors among residents.

2.2 What challenges have you personally experienced in relation to these projects?

The respondent stated, *“Wala naman.”* This indicates that the respondent has not encountered significant issues related to the projects.

3. IMPACT OF INCONSISTENT EXECUTION

3.1. Have you observed any projects that were delayed, discontinued, or inconsistently implemented? Please describe.

The ninth respondent mentioned a construction project in the Sampaguita area that was delayed. The respondent stated, *“Doon naman sa Sampaguita, dapat last 2 months pa dapat tapos yun sa pagkakaalam ko pero ngayon pa lang sinimulan ang*

pagawa.” This suggests that some infrastructure initiatives in the barangay may experience delays in implementation.

3.2. In what ways did unfinished or delayed projects affect the overall condition of the community

The ninth respondent described how ongoing construction affects road conditions during rainy weather. The respondent stated, “Naging maputik ang daan pag umulan at sumikip din ang mga daanan dahil sa mga gamit nila sa construction.” This response highlights how unfinished projects can create inconvenience and safety concerns for residents.

4. OBSTACLES AND TRANSPARENCY ISSUES

4.1 What do you think are the main obstacles preventing the successful implementation of these projects?

The ninth respondent highlighted issues related to budgeting and quality of materials. The participant stated, “Tinipid ang budget kaya napakatagal matapos at substandard ang materials.” This indicates that the resident perceives that budget reductions may lead to delays and the use of low-quality materials, which may cause projects to deteriorate quickly.

4.2. In your view, does transparency play a role in project gaps? Please explain.

The ninth respondent directly expressed that transparency is lacking. The participant stated, “Kulang sila sa transparency.” This short but direct response indicates the resident’s perception that there is insufficient openness regarding barangay projects and activities.

5. EFFECTS ON TRUST AND GOVERNANCE PERCEPTION

5.1. How have these development projects affected your trust in the local government?

The ninth respondent said that everyday experiences significantly influence residents' trust in development projects. Instead of perceiving the projects as beneficial, the respondent associates them with inconvenience and daily frustration. This sentiment is shown when the respondent mentioned that “pumangit ang tiwala kasi dito sa 175 pagpasok at pag-uwi traffic lagi... sayang sa oras.” This suggests that when development initiatives create unintended problems such as traffic congestion, they may negatively affect public perception of government performance.

5.2. How do these experiences shape your overall perception of governance in Barangay 175?

The respondent's perception of governance is shaped by their daily experiences with infrastructure projects in the barangay. The belief that the projects were poorly implemented leads the respondent to question the integrity and effectiveness of leadership. This perception is evident in the statement “araw-araw akong dumadaan sa kalsadang pinagawa nila... naaalala ko kung paano nila tinipid at niloko ang mga tao.” Such experiences can strongly influence residents' trust and perception of public accountability.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT

6.1. What improvements would you recommend for future Sustainable Development Projects?

The response, “*mabilis... mabisang paraan ng pag collection ng basura... para walang bumara... at hindi mag-cause ng traffic,*” provides a detailed explanation of the

consequences of inefficient waste management. The participant links garbage accumulation to blocked drainage systems, which in turn leads to flooding and traffic congestion, especially during rainy periods. This demonstrates a clear awareness of the cause-and-effect relationship between environmental management and daily living conditions. It suggests that improving waste collection is not just about cleanliness but also about preventing broader infrastructural and mobility issues.

6.2. If you were given the opportunity, what project would you prioritize for Barangay 175 and why?

The response, “*urban planning... tamang plano... maayos na kalsada... drainage... segregation ng basura,*” provides a comprehensive critique of the barangay’s structural and environmental issues. The participant links the absence of proper urban planning to problems such as traffic, flooding, and improper waste disposal. This indicates a strong understanding of how systematic planning influences multiple aspects of community life, emphasizing the need for integrated and well-structured development strategies.

Respondent 10

1. PERCEPTION OF LGU SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT PROJECTS

1.1 What Sustainable Development Projects are you aware of in Barangay 175?

The tenth respondent mentioned a cleanliness initiative known as the “*Kalinisan sa Bagong Pilipinas Program.*” This indicates awareness of environmental programs implemented in the barangay.

1.2. In your opinion, do these projects address the real needs of the community? Why or why not?

The tenth respondent expressed that the projects do not fully address the needs of the community. The respondent stated, “*Not really... mas maganda kung*

nagkakaroon ng system or policies na magpo-prohibit sa mga residents sa pagkakalat.”

This response suggests that while clean-up activities exist, stronger policies and community discipline may be needed to effectively address environmental issues.

2. RESIDENTS’ EXPERIENCE WITH IMPLEMENTATION AND SUSTAINABILITY

2.1 Can you describe your personal experience with the implementation of these projects?

The respondent recalled experiencing traffic during a creek construction project. The respondent stated, *“Nagka traffic non kasi one way yung kalsada noong ginagawa nila yung creek.”* This suggests that infrastructure projects may temporarily disrupt transportation and mobility within the community.

2.2 What challenges have you personally experienced in relation to these projects?

The respondent mentioned flooding despite newly constructed drainage systems. The respondent stated, *“Kahit bagong gawa yung mga drainage bumabaha pa din kasi puro basura... kaya maraming sasakyan ang na stranded.”* This indicates that improper waste disposal may undermine infrastructure improvements, contributing to persistent flooding problems.

3. IMPACT OF INCONSISTENT EXECUTION

3.1. Have you observed any projects that were delayed, discontinued, or inconsistently implemented? Please describe.

The tenth respondent reported that they were not aware of any sustainable development projects in the barangay. The respondent stated, “So far, in my best

knowledge wala naman.” This response again reflects limited awareness of barangay initiatives among some residents.

3.2. In what ways did unfinished or delayed projects affect the overall condition of the community

The tenth respondent did not provide an answer regarding the impact of unfinished or delayed projects, which suggests that the respondent may not have observed or experienced any specific effects related to this issue.

4. OBSTACLES AND TRANSPARENCY ISSUES

4.1 What do you think are the main obstacles preventing the successful implementation of these projects?

The tenth respondent suggested that political motives may influence project implementation. The participant explained, “Iba kasi ang goal ng mga politika... not long term growth but just making impression sa tao.” This response indicates that the resident believes some projects may be chosen for their immediate visibility rather than their long-term benefits for the community.

4.2. In your view, does transparency play a role in project gaps? Please explain.

The last respondent compared transparency in governance to transparency within organizations. The participant stated, “People should know bakit may ganon para they can support or give comment for improvement.” This response suggests that the resident believes informing the public about projects and policies can encourage community support and participation.

5. EFFECTS ON TRUST AND GOVERNANCE PERCEPTION

5.1. How have these development projects affected your trust in the local government?

The Last respondent highlights that trust in the local government is strongly influenced by the attitude and dedication of elected officials. When leaders demonstrate genuine service and commitment to the community, residents are more likely to develop confidence in governance. This perspective is reflected in the respondent's statement that "when I see elected officials who act for the community and not only for themselves, they gain my trust." This suggests that ethical leadership and visible dedication to public service play an important role in building trust among residents.

5.2. How do these experiences shape your overall perception of governance in Barangay 175?

This respondent maintains a generally positive perception of governance, recognizing that certain projects provide meaningful benefits to the community. This view is reflected when the respondent stated that "okay naman, may mga project that really help people." This indicates that despite criticisms from other residents, some individuals still acknowledge the positive contributions of barangay programs.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT

6.1. What improvements would you recommend for future Sustainable Development Projects?

The statement, "*look for project na for long term sustainability,*" reflects a forward-looking and strategic perspective on development. The respondent emphasizes the importance of initiatives that provide enduring benefits rather than temporary relief. This suggests a level of awareness that some existing projects may be short-lived or

reactive. The recommendation highlights the need for long-term planning, where sustainability is embedded in the design and implementation of development programs to ensure lasting community impact.

6.2. If you were given the opportunity, what project would you prioritize for Barangay 175 and why?

The statement, *“project about kalinisan... pero ang problema... ang community din ang nagkakalat... gumawa ng system,”* reflects a balanced perspective on waste management by recognizing both institutional and community responsibilities. The respondent acknowledges that while garbage collection systems are important, resident behavior also contributes to the problem. The suggestion to create a system that works for both collectors and residents, especially in hard-to-reach areas, implies the need for collaborative and context-sensitive solutions that address both structural limitations and behavioral factors.

Interpretation of Data

Question #1

Perception of LGU Sustainable Development Projects

Theme 1: Limited and Uneven Awareness of Sustainable Development Projects

The findings reveal that awareness of sustainable development projects in Barangay 175 varies significantly among participants. While some residents were able to mention specific initiatives, several participants expressed little to no awareness of existing projects.

Some participants explicitly stated that they were not aware of any sustainable development initiatives in the barangay. One participant shared, *“Wala, wala akong nararamdaman.”* Another similarly stated, *“Wala akong nakikitang projects.”* These responses suggest a perceived absence or invisibility of projects within the community.

Other participants mentioned limited knowledge, often identifying only one type of assistance such as ayuda or educational support. For instance, one respondent said, *“Wala, ayuda. Yun lang alam ko.”* This indicates that certain residents primarily associate sustainable development efforts with short-term financial or material assistance rather than long-term community programs.

The uneven awareness suggests that while projects may exist, information dissemination and visibility within the community may not be consistent.

Theme 2: Awareness Focused on Environmental, Health, and Educational Initiatives

Despite limited awareness among some participants, several respondents identified specific programs related to environmental cleanliness, healthcare services, and educational assistance.

Environmental initiatives were frequently mentioned. Participants referred to clean-up drives and kalinisan programs conducted weekly or monthly. One participant stated, *“Ang alam ko lang naglilinis sila every Friday, Saturday.”* Another mentioned projects involving the cleaning and rehabilitation of creeks.

Health-related programs were also noted, including free medical check-ups and the establishment of health centers. A participant shared that there were *“free check-ups”* and efforts in *“pagpapatayo ng health centers,”* indicating awareness of community health services.

Educational assistance, such as scholarships and financial aid, was also cited. One respondent mentioned a *“5k once a year educational assistance,”* while another directly identified “Education, Scholarship” as a known initiative.

However, even among those who identified projects, responses suggest that awareness is often limited to observable or directly experienced programs. Some

comments also implied concerns about sustainability and timeliness, such as a participant who noted that road improvements took “10 years bago nagawa.”

Overall, the findings indicate that while certain sustainable development initiatives are recognized particularly in environmental, health, and educational sectors awareness remains inconsistent across residents.

Theme 3: Perceived Limited Effectiveness and Unequal Reach of Projects

The majority of participants expressed that the sustainable development projects in Barangay 175 do not fully address the real needs of the community. Many respondents emphasized issues related to limited reach, lack of consistency, and perceived inequality in implementation.

Several participants directly responded negatively when asked whether the projects address community needs. One participant simply stated, “*Hindi.*” Another remarked, “*Wala, kasi wala nga kasi,*” indicating a perception that no meaningful impact is being felt within the community.

Concerns regarding accessibility and unequal distribution were also raised. One participant shared, “*Hindi ramdam ng tao, hindi lahat nakaka-avail mga ginagawa na programa.*” Similarly, another respondent commented, “*Hindi effective, hindi equal sa pagbibigay.*” These responses suggest that while programs may exist, they are not experienced uniformly across residents.

Some participants also pointed out that visibility through social media does not necessarily translate to actual impact. As one participant expressed, “*Maybe at some point natutugunan siya... hindi lang puro social media posting.*” This indicates a perceived gap between online promotion and tangible implementation.

Environmental efforts such as creek rehabilitation were also questioned in terms of sustainability. A respondent stated that despite improvements, flooding persists, adding, “*Dapat mas nagfocus sila sa tamang pagtatapon ng basura.*” Another

participant suggested that stronger systems or policies should be implemented rather than temporary clean-up activities.

Overall, these responses reflect a perception that while initiatives are present, their effectiveness and inclusivity remain limited.

Theme 4: Conditional Recognition of Positive Impact

Despite the generally critical views, a few participants acknowledged that certain projects do address specific community needs. These positive perceptions were often conditional or limited to particular programs.

For example, one participant affirmed, “Yes, *nakikita ko naman via social media.*” Others cited specific initiatives such as road improvements, medical services, and clean-up drives as beneficial. One respondent noted, “*At some point yes, especially medical and clean-up,*” while another stated, “*Siguro sa project na yun (about kalsada), yes.*”

These responses suggest that while some residents recognize the value of particular initiatives, the overall perception remains mixed. Positive feedback tends to focus on specific, observable projects rather than a comprehensive sense of sustained development.

Question #2

Residents’ Experience with Implementation and Sustainability

Theme 1: Financial Assistance as the Primary Program

The findings indicate that financial assistance is the most tangible and widely recognized form of support experienced by residents. Several participants cited educational assistance and other forms of monetary aid as their primary interaction with barangay programs.

One respondent described the ₱5,000 educational support as a *“malaking bagay, lalong-lalo na sa mga kabataan na naghihikahos,”* emphasizing its importance for struggling students. However, the same participant also noted its limitations, stating, *“Hindi siya sapat, 5k lang yun... dalawang sem lang tayo sa isang taon, dapat twice.”* Another participant shared that family members benefited from barangay assistance, saying that their siblings were able to receive financial support from Barangay 175.

Despite these acknowledgments, financial assistance was often the only program residents could clearly identify. As one participant implied, beyond financial aid, *“wala akong nakikitang iba.”* This suggests that sustainable development initiatives are frequently equated with short-term monetary support rather than long-term or structural programs.

Theme 2: Limited Personal Engagement and Visibility of Barangay Initiatives

A significant number of participants reported minimal or no personal experience with barangay projects. Several responses explicitly conveyed a lack of felt impact. One participant directly stated, *“Wala akong nararamdaman sa kanila,”* while another remarked, *“Parang wala kasi akong nararamdaman na projects.”*

Some respondents attributed visible infrastructure developments such as drainage systems, roads, and health centers to the city government rather than the barangay. As one participant explained, *“Hindi ko talaga ramdam project ng barangay... puro project ng city hall ang nakikita ko.”* This reflects either a lack of clarity regarding jurisdictional responsibilities or limited visibility of barangay-led initiatives.

The findings suggest that while programs may be implemented, their visibility and direct engagement with residents remain uneven. This limited personal engagement contributes to perceptions that the barangay is not actively initiating sustainable development projects.

Theme 3: Perceived Inequality and Selective Distribution of Assistance

Concerns regarding fairness and inclusivity emerged as a prominent theme. Several participants expressed the perception that assistance and resources are not distributed equitably among residents.

One respondent observed that relief goods and cash assistance *“di lahat ng resident ay nata-tap,”* further adding that those who are *“mas malakas”* or *“mas may kapit”* are more likely to receive support. Another participant expressed frustration after an unmet request, stating, *“Minsan nag-request ako diyan, wala talaga,”* and even added, *“Wala na akong pag-asa sa kanila.”*

These accounts point to a perceived pattern of selective distribution, where access to services may be influenced by proximity, relationships, or political alignment. Such perceptions may weaken trust in local governance and raise concerns regarding transparency and accountability in program implementation.

Theme 4: Resource Constraints and Sustainability Challenges

Participants also highlighted limitations in resources and inconsistencies in sustaining project outcomes. While some acknowledged that projects are implemented, they emphasized that available resources are insufficient to meet community needs.

For example, one participant shared an experience of seeking medical assistance, stating that when they requested anti-rabies vaccination support, *“wala silang resources,”* referring to the lack of necessary supplies for a booster shot. Infrastructure-related concerns were also raised. A respondent noted delays in the completion of a multipurpose hall, describing how it is *“naurong nang naurong.”* Another mentioned that despite newly constructed drainage systems, flooding persists because *“puro basura, kaya bumabara.”*

These concerns suggest that while implementation efforts are visible, sustainability is challenged by limited resources, maintenance issues, and systemic

environmental problems. As reflected in residents' experiences, project implementation is present but often constrained in scope, continuity, and long-term effectiveness.

Question #3

Impact of Inconsistent Execution

Theme 1: Limited Awareness and Visibility of Barangay Sustainable Development Projects

Most participants expressed that they were not aware of any sustainable development projects implemented by the barangay. Some residents directly stated that they had not seen any initiatives. One resident stated, "Wala naman." Another mentioned, "Wala, kasi hindi ko naman nakikita si Cap eh." The same respondent further emphasized dissatisfaction with youth leadership, stating, "Ay SK hindi ko maramdaman yan, bakit may SK pa eh wala naman ginagawa dito."

Similarly, another participant explained the lack of observable barangay initiatives, saying, "Hindi ko masabi kung project ng barangay, kase kung pagbabasihan naten ang project ng barangay, wala akong nakikita kase ang kalimitan na binababa is galing National, kung hindi National galing sa City." Another resident also expressed a similar observation, stating, "So far, in my best knowledge wala naman."

These responses suggest that many residents perceive the absence of barangay-led sustainable development initiatives, which may indicate limited visibility, communication, or awareness of local governance programs. Some participants acknowledged existing developments but believed that these projects were implemented by national or city authorities rather than the barangay.

One respondent stated, "Ang nagawa lang na nakita ko is itong sa kanal, eh National naman ang may hawak niyan eh." Despite this, the same participant acknowledged some forms of local support, stating, "Very supportive naman si cap sa mga teachers sa elementary school kapag may program."

This indicates that while some initiatives are visible, residents may not directly attribute them to barangay leadership, which may affect the perceived effectiveness of local governance.

Theme 2: Delayed and Inconsistently Implemented Community Programs

Some residents pointed out that certain social service programs exist but are not implemented consistently. One participant shared, “Sa may educational assistance namen, na kahit naturuloy siya is may times na nire re-schedule.” The same respondent also raised concerns about health services, stating, “May nakikita din akong Health Center, pero walang mga tao so anong silbi non?”

These responses indicate that although services are available, inconsistency in their implementation may reduce their effectiveness and accessibility. Environmental programs were also identified as inconsistent. One participant described a river-cleaning initiative that was not sustained, stating, “Every friday pumupunta sila Palmera para maglinis ilog pero hindi nila napagpatuloy.” The same resident emphasized the consequences of environmental neglect, saying, “Kapag makikita mo sobrang dumi, kapag dadaan ka doon sobrang baho, so paano na lang yung mga dumadaan don.”

Furthermore, the participant stressed the responsibility of leaders to maintain community safety and reputation, explaining, “Siyempre dapat ma maintain nila yung protection or safety ng mga tao na nakatira dito sa barangay at kung sino man yung bibisita dito.” They further added, “Kailangan din natin i maintain yung image, ikaw as politician is nagre reflect yung characteristics mo or kung gaano ka ka-good leader doon san ipinapakita or maipapakita mo sa kaayusan ng community.”

These responses highlight how the discontinuation of environmental programs may negatively affect sanitation, safety, and the public image of the community. Several participants also pointed out delays in infrastructure-related projects. One resident mentioned the delayed construction of a community facility, stating, “Yung regarding sa

Multi purpose Hall na umuurong yung paggawa, pero alam ko dapat this year siya matatapos.”

Another resident expressed concerns regarding road conditions, stating, “Maraming problema lalo ma sa road here in 175, hindi agad naayos ng barangay although hindi sila ang main responsibility taker but meron padin silang i take na action.” Similarly, another participant noted delays in construction within their area, saying, “Doon naman sa Sampaguita, dapat last 2 months pa dapat tapos yun sa pagkakaalam ko pero ngayon pa lang sinimulan ang pagawa.” These findings suggest that infrastructure delays contribute to residents’ perception of inconsistent project execution.

Theme 3: Effects of Inconsistent Project Implementation on the Community

Some participants expressed little concern regarding delayed or unfinished projects. One resident simply stated, “Wala.” Another respondent shared, “Wala din, kase wala naman akong pakielam sa kanila eh.” However, the same participant acknowledged that projects could still affect the community, explaining, “Pero kung meron silang ginawa, pwede maka apekto yon sa community at pwede din hindi rin makatulong kase wala nga eh.” These responses suggest that some residents may feel disengaged from local governance activities.

Environmental concerns were also raised in relation to unfinished or inactive programs. One participant explained, “Sa basura na yan, meron na silang truck dati dito kaso hindi naman nag f function.” Another resident emphasized the risks of an unclean environment, stating, “Sobrang risky ng ganon eh, makita mo madumi yung kapaligiran mo tapos mabaho is parang mawawalan siguro sila ng gana.”

The same participant added a call for community awareness, saying, “I just hope na makakapag reflect yung mga tao sa nakikita nila hindi yung patuloy na magbubulag-bulagan sila.” These responses indicate that inconsistent environmental management can negatively affect sanitation and community morale.

Some residents expressed disappointment regarding unfulfilled expectations for community improvements. One participant stated, “Nag expect kami na magkaroon ng implementation sa street light eh kaso wala.” The same respondent added, “Meron man kaya lang hindi naman namin nakikita, kase ang katwiran nila is malapit kame sa isang politician.” They further explained their limited interaction with the barangay office, saying, “Nakakapunta lang kame sa barangay kapag kukuha ng papel.” These responses highlight concerns about perceived inequality in project implementation and limited engagement between residents and local officials.

Some residents described the difficulties caused by inadequate infrastructure maintenance. One participant stated, “Madaming tao ang nahihirapan kapag hindi naayos yung lugar nila.” The same resident further explained, “Sa may Matarik o Robes, binabaha sila kapag malakas yung ulan, so throughout that day ang iisipin nila is kung papaano sila makakalikas.” This indicates that delays in addressing infrastructure problems may expose residents to flooding risks and safety concerns.

Ongoing or delayed construction projects also created disturbances for residents. One participant shared, “Maingay siya tuwing gabi or every time na may ginagawa sila, so ang nangyayari sa mga tao is hindi sila makatulog agad.” Transportation difficulties were also reported. One resident stated, “Sa may Camarin to NHA area, medyo hassle yung pag travel around this area.”

Similarly, another respondent explained, “Naging maputik ang daan pag umulan at sumikip din ang mga daanan dahil sa mga gamit nila sa construction.” These responses show that unfinished or delayed projects may disrupt mobility, create noise disturbances, and affect residents’ daily routines.

Question # 4

Obstacles and Transparency Issues

Theme 1: Governance Failures and Political Practices as Barriers to Effective Project Implementation

The responses of the residents reveal that the unsuccessful implementation of projects is largely attributed to governance-related issues. Although one participant mentioned "*siguro lack of funds,*" most responses suggest that the problem is not simply the absence of budget, but how it is managed and implemented.

The most noticeable issue was corruption. It was specifically mentioned by a number of participants as the main challenge. "*Corruption, yun ang number one kasi magkukulang ang pondo kapag ganon,*" a resident said, describing how projects become "*putol-putol*" or unfinished because money is allegedly stolen along the way. Another respondent firmly stated, "*corruption, di na yan mawawala,*" demonstrating a strong belief that financial mismanagement is widespread and built into society. These claims support the idea that a major problem influencing project completion and quality is financial mismanagement.

Favoritism and unequal distribution of benefits were also emphasized. A resident shared, "*dito pag may kakilala ka sa barangay yun lang yung nabibigyan nila*" implying that access to programs may be dependent on personal relationships. This perception reflects concerns about fairness and transparency in allocation of resources.

Another significant aspect identified was leadership accountability. One respondent observed, "*Sa leadership—kasi nandyan naman yung budget, nandyan naman lahat. Wala paring implementation.*" This means that resources may be accessible, but execution is not satisfactory. Similarly, another participant stated that officials had the authority to approve and implement projects, but "*they choose not to,*" supporting the idea that the absence of strong political will and responsibility contributes

to project failure.

Locals think that ethical and governance problems, not a lack of funding, are the primary causes of community initiative failures. They made the argument that some politicians prioritize short-term, conspicuous projects over sustainable growth in order to boost their public image. Concerns were also voiced regarding the usage of substandard supplies and delayed completion as a result of budget cuts, which resulted in ineffective resource use. The main obstacles to a project's successful execution are often thought to be corruption, bias, poor accountability, short-term political motivations, and ineffective budget management, which highlights the necessity of openness, greater leadership accountability, and long-term planning.

Theme 2: Lack of Genuine Transparency as a Contributor to Project Gaps

Residents' comments indicate that transparency is viewed as a crucial element contributing to gaps in project implementation. While a few participants mentioned the presence of visible reports, the majority of respondents indicated that openness is either insufficient or not truly practiced.

Several residents highlighted how important transparency is in maintaining accountability. A participant said, "*Yan ang importante sa ngayon, kailangan transparent kung saan ginagamit ang pera,*" emphasizing the necessity of publicly exposing how funds are used. Another respondent stated that transparency enables constituents to understand the actions of the barangay, stating that it is important "*para yung mga nasasakupan ng kapitan alam yung kilos sa loob ng barangay.*" These statements support the notion that openness in governance increases public trust and awareness.

However, several participants stated that transparency is failing in actual practice. One resident stated, "*yes, pero dito wala namang transparency na nangyayari*" while another simply stated, "*Kulang sila sa transparency.*" These direct responses further strengthen the perception that information about projects and fund allocations is not fully accessible or clearly communicated to the community.

Interestingly, one participant remarked that reports are put on a bulletin board but questioned their authenticity: *"Nandoon yung lahat, but nandon ba yung actions? Hindi naman naramdaman ng mga residente."* This implies that, while documentation exists, locals do not feel the full impact of the stated initiatives. The disparity between stated successes and lived experiences reveals a perceived mismatch between formal transparency and real implementation.

The community have expressed disappointment for elected officials, bringing up examples of poor leadership visibility, such failing to attend public events, and speculating that even publicly available financial records might contain *"kickbacks."* They see transparency as requiring more than just financial disclosure; it also calls for responsible and proactive leadership. In order to promote involvement and support, participants stressed that residents should be informed about programs and policy changes, much like in organizational settings. In general, mistrust and project gaps are caused by insufficient and ambiguous transparency procedures, underscoring the need for greater sincere openness in reporting, decision-making, and leadership accountability to boost community participation and confidence

Question # 5

Effects on Trust and Governance Perception

Theme 1: Project Performance Directly Influences Public Trust in Local Government

The responses reveal that development projects significantly shape residents' level of trust in the local government. Trust appears to be closely tied to the quality, consistency, and fairness of project implementation. While a few participants expressed increased trust, the majority conveyed declining or negative perceptions.

Some respondents shared that effective projects strengthen their confidence in the barangay. One participant stated, *"mas nagiging trusted sa mga projects,"* indicating

that visible and beneficial initiatives can enhance trust. Another explained that when services and programs are delivered properly, *“may trust ka sakanila na gagawin nila yung tama.”* Similarly, a respondent mentioned that when elected officials genuinely act for the community and show passion in serving people, they gain trust. These statements validate the idea that competence and sincere public service positively influence public perception.

Despite this, the majority of answers indicated dissatisfaction and decreased trust. *“Wala na akong trust”* and *“wala nang tiwala”* were two phrases used by several participants to describe their obvious lack of trust. One person even voiced a want for a change in leadership, believing that doing so would help the situation. These answers reveal a great deal of disappointment and despair.

Another factor influencing confidence was consistency in project execution. According to one participant, *“unti-unting nababawasan yung tiwala natin”* occurs when officials fail to deliver projects consistently or break trust. This implies that confidence is not only established through a single successful program but also maintained through consistent and dependable performance.

Some residents feel neglected and excluded, particularly when assistance programs appear to bypass them, leading to detachment and reduced civic engagement. Frustrations over unresolved infrastructure issues, such as ongoing traffic problems, also contribute to dissatisfaction. Overall, the findings show that trust in local government depends on how effectively and inclusively development projects are implemented. When projects address real community needs, trust increases; when neglect and inefficiency persist, distrust and disengagement grow.

Theme 2: Positive and Moderate Perceptions Based on Direct Experience

The people' experiences have created various but usually critical perspectives of the government in Barangay 175. While several participants acknowledged advances and constructive initiatives, many were concerned about corruption, leadership

standards, and implementation failures. Several people gave favorable remarks based on personal experience.

One participant stated that they frequently observe projects because their mother works in the barangay, allowing them to see progress directly. Another respondent classified the governance as *"Okay naman,"* pointing out that there are projects that actually benefit people. These replies show that direct involvement or accessibility to barangay operations can result in a more balanced or positive opinion.

However, many individuals provided mild to negative feedback. One citizen assessed the governance as *"50 out of 100,"* signifying ordinary or poor performance. Another clearly stated, *"Kailangan ng malaking pagbabago,"* indicating a strong desire for reform.

Theme 3: Critical Views Rooted in Perceived Corruption and Leadership Gaps

Experiences with perceived corruption had a strong negative impact on attitudes. A participant who completed on-the-job training at the barangay stated that during rice distribution, barangay authorities were the first to get supply. This firsthand observation molded their conviction that corruption occurs within the system. Similarly, another responder voiced dissatisfaction with infrastructure projects, claiming that daily travel on badly constructed roads reminds them of cost-cutting and lying. These firsthand experiences have a significant impact on their sense of leadership integrity.

Leadership standards and expectations also played a role. One respondent, who grew up as a student leader, explained that having a higher standard of leadership makes them more critical of how barangay officials manage programs and processes. According to this perspective, awareness of governance procedures makes it easier to identify gaps and shortcomings.

Some people voiced their dissatisfaction with the barangay captain, citing management and leadership inefficiencies. In general, Barangay 175 inhabitants'

perceptions of governance are influenced by their own experiences and expectations. Many people continue to be critical because of worries about corruption, inadequate accountability, and poor project execution, even while some acknowledge good attempts.

Question # 6

Recommendations for Improvement

Theme 1: Improvement of Basic Social Services and Infrastructure

A dominant theme in the responses is the need to improve essential services and infrastructure. Several participants pointed out issues related to housing, flooding, and waste management. For example, one respondent mentioned, “*Pabahay? Kasi marami dito... nangungupahan siguro.*” This highlights the need for housing assistance for renters in the community.

Another participant emphasized flood control, stating, “*Unahin ang pagkakaayos ng mga binabahang lugar (flood control).*” This suggests that flooding is a recurring issue that affects residents’ safety and daily life.

Similarly, waste management was repeatedly mentioned, such as “*Mabilis maayos at mabisang paraan ng pag collection ng mga basura sa daan.*” This indicates concerns about sanitation, road accessibility, and even traffic problems during heavy rains.

Theme 2: Governance, Transparency, and Accountability

Another strong theme centers on improving governance and project implementation. Respondents did not only focus on what projects should be implemented, but also on how they should be managed. One participant clearly stated,

“Be consistent with their own projects.” This implies that there may be issues with continuity or follow-through in past initiatives.

Another respondent emphasized, *“Transparency and mas maagap na pagpapagawa ng mga infrastructures at mas maayos na governance.”* This reflects the community’s desire for openness, accountability, and efficiency from local leaders.

Additionally, concerns about aid distribution were expressed through the statement, *“Yung mga ayuda is dapat natatanggap ng mga mamamayan mismo at sapat, hindi kulang-kulang.”* This suggests that residents want fair and sufficient allocation of resources.

Theme 3: Peace and Order as a Foundation of Development

Peace and security were also mentioned as important components of sustainable development. One respondent simply stated, *“Gusto ko lang... yung curfew.”* Another highlighted *“Peace and Order nga.”* These responses show that residents associate discipline and community safety with overall development.

Theme 4: Education and Human Capital Development

Education emerged as another significant theme, particularly in relation to financial assistance for students. One participant suggested, *“Educational assistance, taasan nila, sa college dapat dyan twice yan.”*

This indicates that residents recognize education as a long-term investment and a pathway for social mobility.

Theme 5: Long-Term Sustainability and Resource Mobilization

Some participants emphasized the importance of sustainability and strategic

planning. For instance, one respondent recommended, *“Look for project na for long term sustainability.”* Another suggested, *“Kumuha ng mga sponsors para mapunan ang mga resources.”*

These responses show an awareness that development projects should not only address immediate needs but also ensure continuity and sufficient funding.

Gap Analysis Between Policy Intentions and Community Experience

This section presents a critical analysis of the discrepancies between the intended objectives of Sustainable Development Projects (SDPs) and the lived experiences of residents in Barangay 175. Based on the thematic findings across Research Questions 1 to 6, several structural, procedural, and perceptual gaps emerged. While policy intentions reflect principles of inclusivity, sustainability, transparency, and long-term development, community narratives reveal inconsistencies in execution, accessibility, and impact.

1. Policy Intention: Inclusive and Community-Wide Awareness Vs. Community Experience: Limited Visibility and Uneven Awareness

Sustainable development initiatives are intended to be inclusive and widely communicated so that residents are aware of ongoing programs and can actively participate in them. However, the findings show a significant awareness gap.

Multiple participants expressed statements such as *“Wala akong nararamdaman”* and *“Wala akong nakikitang projects.”* This indicates not necessarily the total absence of projects, but rather the absence of felt impact and visibility at the grassroots level.

Even when projects were identified, awareness was often limited to observable activities like clean-up drives or educational assistance. This suggests that communication mechanisms may not be effectively reaching all residents.

There is a disconnect between documented implementation and experiential awareness. Development that is not visible, understood, or personally experienced by residents fails to achieve its intended inclusive purpose.

2. Policy Intention: Long-Term Sustainable Development Vs. Community Experience: Short-Term Financial Assistance Dominance

Sustainable Development Projects are theoretically designed to create structural, long-term improvements aligned with broader sustainability principles such as those promoted by the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals. These include improvements in infrastructure, environmental systems, health services, and human capital development.

However, residents frequently equated sustainable development with short-term financial assistance, particularly the ₱5,000 educational aid. While appreciated, respondents described it as insufficient and irregular. One participant emphasized that it should be provided twice a year to be more effective.

This reflects a narrowing of development perception—from comprehensive sustainability to monetary relief.

There is a shift from long-term structural transformation to short-term assistance programs. The intended sustainability dimension of policies appears reduced in practice to temporary support mechanisms rather than systemic reform.

3. Policy Intention: Equity and Fair Distribution Vs. Community Experience: Perceived Favoritism and Selective Access

Inclusive governance requires that programs be distributed fairly, particularly to vulnerable sectors. However, several participants raised concerns that not all residents can access services equally.

Statements referencing “hindi lahat nakaka-avail” and observations about those with “mas may kapit” receiving assistance point to perceptions of favoritism and political bias.

These perceptions were reinforced by personal experiences where requests for assistance were denied or ignored.

While policies aim for equitable distribution, community narratives suggest selective implementation. Even the perception of inequality is enough to weaken trust and reduce legitimacy of programs.

4. Policy Intention: Efficient and Timely Project Implementation Vs. Community Experience: Delays, Interruptions, and Incomplete Projects

Infrastructure and service delivery are expected to follow clear timelines and continuity plans. Yet, participants reported delayed construction of the multipurpose hall, road repair postponements, rescheduled educational assistance, and discontinued environmental clean-up efforts.

Flooding remains persistent despite drainage improvements. Health centers were described as physically present but sometimes without personnel.

These examples demonstrate that while projects may begin, consistency and follow-through remain problematic. Implementation gaps weaken sustainability. Delays and interruptions diminish credibility and reduce the long-term effectiveness of initiatives.

5. Policy Intention: Transparency and Accountability Vs. Community Experience: Formal Reporting but Limited Felt Transparency

Governance frameworks emphasize transparency through public reporting and visible documentation. Some residents acknowledged posted financial reports; however, many questioned their authenticity and practical impact.

Participants repeatedly cited corruption, misuse of funds, and political motivations as barriers. One participant questioned whether posted reports reflect actual implementation, suggesting that transparency must be felt, not just documented.

There is a difference between procedural transparency (reports, postings) and experiential transparency (visible outcomes, tangible improvements). The community perceives a gap between what is reported and what is experienced.

6. Policy Intention: Improved Quality of Life Vs. Community Experience: Continued Environmental and Infrastructure Struggles

The ultimate goal of sustainable development is to enhance overall quality of life. However, residents continue to report flooding, waste accumulation, travel inconvenience, construction noise, and sanitation issues.

These persistent daily challenges indicate that development outcomes are either insufficient in scale or not maintained consistently. Despite policy objectives aimed at community improvement, lived realities show ongoing structural problems that directly affect safety, comfort, and mobility.

Summary of Findings

1. What is the perception of the residents of Barangay 175 in Caloocan City about the Sustainable Development Projects carried out by the Local Government Units (LGUs)?

Findings reveal limited and uneven awareness of sustainable development initiatives among residents. While some identified environmental clean-up drives, health services, road improvements, and educational assistance, many expressed little to no awareness of projects in their barangay. Sustainable development was commonly associated with short-term financial assistance rather than long-term community programs. Overall, perceptions were mixed, with many residents questioning the

effectiveness, inclusivity, and visibility of initiatives.

2. What have been the experiences of the people of Barangay 175 with the implementation and sustainability of Sustainable Development Projects in their area?

Residents' experiences were largely centered on financial assistance programs, particularly educational aid. However, many reported limited personal engagement with other barangay-led initiatives. Concerns about unequal distribution, favoritism, and insufficient resources were common. Delays in infrastructure projects, lack of medical supplies, and persistent flooding highlighted sustainability challenges. While programs exist, their continuity and long-term effectiveness appear constrained.

3. How do residents describe the impact of the inconsistent execution of Sustainable Development Projects on their daily activities and the overall quality of the community?

Inconsistent execution of sustainable development initiatives in Barangay 175 is reflected in the limited visibility of barangay-led projects, delays in infrastructure development, discontinued environmental programs, and inconsistencies in social services. While some residents reported minimal awareness or concern, others described significant impacts such as poor sanitation, flooding risks, transportation difficulties, noise disturbances, and unmet expectations for community improvement. These findings highlight the importance of consistent implementation, transparency, and sustained community engagement in order to achieve effective and sustainable local development.

4. What obstacles do residents link to the gaps in the Sustainable Development related initiatives in Barangay 175?

Residents identified governance-related concerns as primary obstacles. Perceived corruption, favoritism, weak accountability, political motivations, and

ineffective budget management were frequently mentioned. Although some acknowledged possible funding limitations, most believed that mismanagement and poor leadership were greater barriers than lack of resources.

5. In what ways do these gaps affect the community's trust, engagement, and general view of local government?

The identified gaps between policy intentions and community experiences significantly influence the community's trust, engagement, and overall perception of the local government in Barangay 175. When residents perceive inconsistencies in project implementation, unequal distribution of assistance, delayed infrastructure development, and limited transparency, their confidence in governance tends to decline. Repeated experiences of unmet expectations and perceived favoritism contribute to skepticism toward official programs and weaken trust in leadership. As a result, some residents express disengagement or reduced participation in barangay initiatives because they feel that their concerns are not sufficiently addressed. Although certain projects such as educational assistance, clean-up drives, and health services are acknowledged, the persistence of structural issues and communication gaps overshadows these positive efforts. Overall, these gaps shape a general view of local government that is mixed but often critical, where trust becomes conditional on visible, consistent, and equitable action rather than solely on policy announcements or documented reports.

6. What do residents recommend to enhance the planning, execution, and longevity of future development initiatives in their barangay?

Based on the responses of the residents, it can be interpreted that they recommend a more community-centered, transparent, and long-term approach in enhancing the planning, execution, and sustainability of future development initiatives in the barangay. In terms of planning, residents emphasized prioritizing basic and urgent needs such as housing, flood control, waste management, peace and order, and educational assistance, suggesting that projects should be grounded on the actual conditions experienced by the community. For execution, participants highlighted the

importance of transparency, consistency, faster implementation of infrastructure, proper distribution of aid, and stricter enforcement of policies, which reflect concerns about accountability and efficiency in governance. Lastly, for longevity, residents expressed the need for sustainable and well-funded programs, including long-term projects and investment in education, to ensure that development efforts create lasting impact rather than temporary solutions. Overall, the findings show that residents are not only asking for more projects, but for better-planned, properly implemented, and sustainable initiatives that genuinely respond to their lived realities.

Chapter 5

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter presents the summary of findings from the gathered and analyzed data, the conclusions drawn from the findings and recommendations offered by the researcher in the light of the findings and conclusions.

Summary of Findings

This study explored the perceptions of the residents of Barangay 175 regarding the effects of sustainable development projects within their community. The respondents of the study were ten (10) residents who have lived in the barangay for at least fifteen years.

What is the perception of the residents of Barangay 175 regarding LGU Sustainable Development Projects?

The findings show that many residents have limited awareness of sustainable development projects implemented in Barangay 175. While some participants were able to identify initiatives such as clean-up drives, medical check-ups, and educational assistance, several respondents expressed that they are not aware of any projects or do not feel their presence in the community.

Furthermore, the findings indicate that perceptions of effectiveness vary among

residents. Some participants believe that certain programs, particularly those related to health and environmental initiatives, address community needs. However, a significant number of respondents expressed that these projects are not fully effective, not equally distributed, or not consistently experienced by all residents. Overall, the findings suggest that although sustainable development initiatives exist, there remains a noticeable gap between implementation and the actual experiences of residents, particularly in terms of visibility, accessibility, and perceived effectiveness.

What have been the experiences of the people of Barangay 175 with the implementation and sustainability of Sustainable Development Projects in their area?

Residents' experiences were largely centered on financial assistance programs, particularly educational aid. However, many reported limited personal engagement with other barangay-led initiatives. Concerns about unequal distribution, favoritism, and insufficient resources were common. Delays in infrastructure projects, lack of medical supplies, and persistent flooding highlighted sustainability challenges. While programs exist, their continuity and long-term effectiveness appear constrained.

How do residents describe the impact of the inconsistent execution of Sustainable Development Projects on their daily activities and the overall quality of the community?

Inconsistent execution of sustainable development initiatives in Barangay 175 is reflected in the limited visibility of barangay-led projects, delays in infrastructure development, discontinued environmental programs, and inconsistencies in social services. While some residents reported minimal awareness or concern, others described significant impacts such as poor sanitation, flooding risks, transportation difficulties, noise disturbances, and unmet expectations for community improvement. These findings highlight the importance of consistent implementation, transparency, and sustained community engagement in order to achieve effective and sustainable local development.

What obstacles do residents link to the gaps in the Sustainable Development related

initiatives in Barangay 175?

Residents identified governance-related concerns as primary obstacles. Perceived corruption, favoritism, weak accountability, political motivations, and ineffective budget management were frequently mentioned. Although some acknowledged possible funding limitations, most believed that mismanagement and poor leadership were greater barriers than lack of resources.

In what ways do these gaps affect the community's trust, engagement, and general view of local government?

The identified gaps between policy intentions and community experiences significantly influence the community's trust, engagement, and overall perception of the local government in Barangay 175. When residents perceive inconsistencies in project implementation, unequal distribution of assistance, delayed infrastructure development, and limited transparency, their confidence in governance tends to decline. Repeated experiences of unmet expectations and perceived favoritism contribute to skepticism toward official programs and weaken trust in leadership. As a result, some residents express disengagement or reduced participation in barangay initiatives because they feel that their concerns are not sufficiently addressed. Although certain projects such as educational assistance, clean-up drives, and health services are acknowledged, the persistence of structural issues and communication gaps overshadows these positive efforts. Overall, these gaps shape a general view of local government that is mixed but often critical, where trust becomes conditional on visible, consistent, and equitable action rather than solely on policy announcements or documented reports.

What do residents recommend to enhance the planning, execution, and longevity of future development initiatives in their barangay?

Based on the responses of the residents, it can be interpreted that they recommend a more community-centered, transparent, and long-term approach in enhancing the planning, execution, and sustainability of future development initiatives in

the barangay. In terms of planning, residents emphasized prioritizing basic and urgent needs such as housing, flood control, waste management, peace and order, and educational assistance, suggesting that projects should be grounded on the actual conditions experienced by the community. For execution, participants highlighted the importance of transparency, consistency, faster implementation of infrastructure, proper distribution of aid, and stricter enforcement of policies, which reflect concerns about accountability and efficiency in governance. Lastly, for longevity, residents expressed the need for sustainable and well-funded programs, including long-term projects and investment in education, to ensure that development efforts create lasting impact rather than temporary solutions. Overall, the findings show that residents are not only asking for more projects, but for better-planned, properly implemented, and sustainable initiatives that genuinely respond to their lived realities.

Conclusion

This study examined the perceptions of the residents of Barangay 175 regarding the effects of sustainable development projects implemented in their community. The findings of the study reveal that residents of Barangay 175 generally have limited and uneven awareness of sustainable development projects implemented by the local government. While some participants were able to identify initiatives related to environmental, health, and educational programs, many respondents expressed that they either lack awareness or do not feel the presence of these projects in their community. Furthermore, perceptions regarding the effectiveness of these initiatives vary, with several residents indicating concerns about unequal access, limited impact, and inconsistency in implementation. Overall, the results suggest that although sustainable development efforts exist, there is a disconnect between program implementation and the actual experiences of residents, highlighting the need for improved visibility, inclusiveness, and consistency in delivering community-based initiatives.

The findings indicate that while some barangay projects, particularly financial

assistance, provide meaningful support to certain residents, their implementation remains limited and inconsistently experienced across the community. Beneficiaries recognize the value of such aid in addressing educational and daily expenses; however, many respondents reported little to no direct experience with barangay-led initiatives and instead associate visible developments, such as infrastructure and health services, with the city government. Additionally, several challenges were identified, including unequal distribution of assistance, perceived favoritism, inadequate resources, poor communication, delays in project implementation, and limited responsiveness to community concerns. These issues suggest the need for improved transparency, equitable service delivery, better resource allocation, and stronger community engagement to enhance the overall effectiveness and inclusivity of barangay projects.

Awareness of sustainable development projects in Barangay 175 is generally low, as many respondents reported little to no knowledge of existing initiatives. This lack of awareness is often associated with limited visibility of barangay leadership and perceived inactivity of local programs. Some residents also believe that most projects are initiated and implemented by national or city-level authorities rather than by the barangay itself. Although a few programs such as educational assistance, health services, environmental clean-up activities, and infrastructure projects were identified, these were commonly described as inconsistent, delayed, or poorly implemented. Issues such as rescheduling of services, absence of personnel in facilities, and discontinuation of environmental efforts were noted. Delays in infrastructure projects, including road repairs and construction, were also highlighted. The impact of these inconsistencies varies among residents; while some expressed indifference, others reported significant challenges such as poor waste management, lack of basic services, flooding and safety risks, environmental concerns, noise disturbances, and transportation difficulties. Overall, the results indicate that inconsistent execution of projects contributes to low public awareness, reduced trust in barangay governance, and negative effects on the community's environmental condition, safety, and overall quality of life.

Barangay project implementation is mainly hindered by governance-related problems such as corruption, favoritism, weak leadership, and poor management of resources rather than a simple lack of funds. Transparency is thought to be essential but it is frequently viewed as incomplete or insufficient, which lessens its potential to guarantee accountability. In general, better project outcomes and fewer implementation gaps require more effective leadership, good governance, and actual transparency. Concerns regarding unfinished projects, delayed execution, and people's unequal access to programs are other manifestations of these problems. Although public postings and other transparency measures are acknowledged, they are frequently seen as lacking for completely informing or involving the community. This emphasizes the necessity for active and significant transparency procedures as well as improved project monitoring and assessment to guarantee that resources are used effectively.

The way in which projects are completed and officials carry out their obligations has a significant impact on the barangay's reputation. When projects are effective, dependable, and inclusive, trust develops; nevertheless, difficulties like corruption, poor leadership, and unmet expectations cause confidence to fall. Despite some locals' neutral or favorable sentiments based on personal experiences, the prevailing perception remains unfavorable. This suggests that regaining and maintaining public trust necessitates constant performance, equality, and transparency. Furthermore, people's personal experiences, such as viewing project outcomes or participating in barangay activities, influence their attitudes. While positive and transparent activities can gradually restore confidence, negative experiences, such as perceived unfairness and a lack of evident results, tend to build mistrust. This shows that trust is not only based on promises but also on consistent and observable actions from local officials.

Based on the responses to Questions 6.1 and 6.2, it is clearly stated that residents of Barangay 175 prioritize development initiatives that address both immediate community needs and long-term sustainability. The findings reveal a strong emphasis on essential services such as housing, healthcare, waste management, infrastructure, and peace and order, indicating that residents seek practical solutions to

everyday challenges. At the same time, there is a clear demand for improved governance characterized by transparency, accountability, and consistency in project implementation. Residents also highlight the importance of inclusive and sustainable strategies, including livelihood support, education, and community participation. Overall, the results suggest that effective development in the barangay requires a holistic approach that integrates responsive planning, efficient execution, and long-term sustainability to ensure meaningful and lasting impact.

RECOMMENDATION

The following recommendations are drawn from the findings of the study to address the identified gaps between policy intentions and the lived experiences of residents in Barangay 175. These aim to improve the implementation, transparency, and sustainability of development initiatives, as well as strengthen community engagement. The recommendations may also serve as a reference for future studies on sustainable development and local governance.

Improve awareness, inclusiveness, and effectiveness of sustainable development projects. The findings of the study revealed that several residents have limited awareness of existing projects, while others perceive that these initiatives do not fully address the real needs of the community or are not equally accessible to all. Many participants expressed that some programs are not felt by the majority and are only visible through social media rather than actual experience. Therefore, barangay officials are encouraged to strengthen information dissemination using multiple platforms and ensure that development initiatives are aligned with the actual needs of residents through regular consultations. In addition, promoting fair and inclusive implementation of projects can help ensure that all sectors of the community benefit. Strengthening the actual execution of programs beyond online promotion can also improve residents' overall perception and trust in sustainable development efforts.

The Barangay 175 is recommended to adopt an inclusive and community-centered approach by prioritizing programs and services that address the

needs of marginalized residents. Transparency, accountability, and equitable resource distribution should be strengthened to ensure fair access to assistance and projects. Enhancing project monitoring, timely implementation, and clear communication with residents can improve awareness and participation. Encouraging citizen involvement in decision-making and feedback mechanisms can build trust and engagement. Coordinated planning with city authorities and stakeholders, along with investment in social and infrastructural programs, will help ensure sustainable and impactful development across all sectors of Barangay 175.

The barangay can strengthen the consistency and visibility of its sustainable development initiatives by improving planning, monitoring, and continuity of projects to ensure they are completed and maintained effectively. The barangay should enhance communication strategies by regularly informing residents about ongoing and upcoming programs through meetings, announcements, and social media to increase awareness and participation. Strengthening coordination with national and city agencies is also important to clearly define responsibilities and ensure timely implementation of infrastructure and community services. Additionally, the barangay should prioritize essential services such as waste management, flood control, road maintenance, and health services to address the immediate needs of residents. Encouraging community involvement and feedback mechanisms can also help improve accountability and ensure that projects are responsive to the actual needs of the community, ultimately leading to better trust, engagement, and overall development outcomes.

The Barangay officials of Barangay 175 should make sure that funds are properly monitored and that regulations against corruption and favoritism are strictly observed in order to strengthen accountability. Transparency should extend beyond bulletin boards by offering reports on project plans, costs, and results that are understandable, comprehensive, and easily publicly accessible. To encourage involvement and guarantee that projects meet real community needs, regular community discussions and feedback systems should be implemented.

It is advised that the authorities of barangay 175 to concentrate on producing reliable, excellent initiatives that have a real beneficial effect on the community. Rebuilding trust can be facilitated by improving communication with locals, making sure resources are distributed fairly, and exhibiting clear leadership participation. Also, strengthening community engagement and public perception can be achieved by fostering transparency and citizen participation in decision-making processes.

The Barangay 175 is recommended to adopt a community-centered and needs-based approach by prioritizing essential services such as housing, healthcare, waste management, flood control, and peace and order. The barangay should also strengthen transparency, accountability, and consistency in project implementation to build trust and ensure effective delivery of services. Improvements in infrastructure and environmental management, particularly in garbage collection, drainage, and urban planning, are necessary to address flooding and sanitation issues. Additionally, promoting inclusive economic opportunities through livelihood programs and support for informal workers can enhance residents' stability. Investment in education and healthcare should also be prioritized to support long-term development. Lastly, the barangay should focus on sustainable and well-coordinated planning, including partnerships with external stakeholders and active community participation, to ensure lasting and impactful development initiatives.

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APPENDICES

Appendix A

Questionnaire

Age: _____

Sex:

- Male
- Female
- Prefer not to say

Civil Status:

- Single
- Married
- Widowed
- Separated

Years of Residency in Barangay 175:

- 1–5 years
- 6–10 years
- 11–20 years
- 21 years and above

Highest Educational Attainment:

- Elementary
- High School
- Senior High School

College

Postgraduate

1. PERCEPTION OF LGU SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT PROJECTS

1.1. What Sustainable Development Projects are you aware of in Barangay 175?

1.2. In your opinion, do these projects address the real needs of the community? Why or why not?

2. RESIDENTS' EXPERIENCE WITH IMPLEMENTATION AND SUSTAINABILITY

2.1. Can you describe your personal experience with the implementation of these projects?

2.2. What challenges have you personally experienced in relation to these projects?

3. IMPACT OF INCONSISTENT EXECUTION

3.1. Have you observed any projects that were delayed, discontinued, or inconsistently implemented? Please describe.

3.2. In what ways did unfinished or delayed projects affect the overall condition of the community?

4. OBSTACLES LINKED TO GAPS IN SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT INITIATIVES

4.1. What do you think are the main obstacles preventing the successful implementation of these projects?

4.2. In your view, does transparency play a role in project gaps? Please explain.

5.. EFFECTS ON TRUST, ENGAGEMENT, AND VIEW OF LOCAL GOVERNMENT

5.1. How have these development projects affected your trust in the local government?

5.2. How do these experiences shape your overall perception of governance in Barangay 175?

6.. RECOMMENDATIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT

6.1. What improvements would you recommend for future Sustainable Development Projects?

6.2. If you were given the opportunity, what project would you prioritize for Barangay 175 and why

Appendix B

Answered Questionnaire

Respondent 1

1.1. What Sustainable Development Projects are you aware of in Barangay 175?

“Education, Scholarship”

1.2. In your opinion, do these projects address the real needs of the community? Why or why not?

"Yes, nakikita ko naman via social media."

2.1 Can you describe your personal experience with the implementation of these projects?

“Sa side ko, wala namang inconsistent. sa mga kapatid ko kasi nabibigyan sila ng financial support ng barangay 175. “

2.2. What challenges have you personally experienced in relation to these projects?

“Requirements”

3.1. Have you observed any projects that were delayed, discontinued, or inconsistently implemented? Please describe.

“Wala naman”

3.2. In what ways did unfinished or delayed projects affect the overall condition of the community?

“Wala”

4.1. What do you think are the main obstacles preventing the successful implementation of these projects?

"Siguro lack of funds."

4.2. In your view, does transparency play a role in project gaps? Please explain.

"Yes, and dito may transparency, nandyan may bulletin board sila sa loob ng barangay."

5.1. How have these development projects affected your trust in the local government?

"mas nagiging trusted sa mga projects."

5.2. How do these experiences shape your overall perception of governance in Barangay 175?

"Saksi kasi ako lagi sa mga project na nagaganap dito, personal experience kasi si mother taga barangay rin... So nakikita namin yung mga improvements."

6.1. What improvements would you recommend for future Sustainable Development Projects?

"Siguro ano.... Pabahay? Kasi marami dito.. ano eh, nangungupahan siguro."

6.2. If you were given the opportunity, what project would you prioritize for Barangay 175 and why?

"Pabahay and Livelihood Training"

Respondent 2

1.1. What Sustainable Development Projects are you aware of in Barangay 175?

"Wala, Wala akong nararamdaman."

1.2. In your opinion, do these projects address the real needs of the community? Why or why not?

"Wala, kasi wala nga kasi"

2.1 Can you describe your personal experience with the implementation of these projects?

“Hindi ko nga alam bakit ganun, wala akong naramdam sa kanila eh. Nakakuha ako financial solo parent pero sa DSWD.”

2.2. What challenges have you personally experienced in relation to these projects?

“Walang experience. Wala na akong pag-asa sa kanila, minsan nag-request ako diyan, wala talaga.”

3.1. Have you observed any projects that were delayed, discontinued, or inconsistently implemented? Please describe.

“Wala, kasi hindi ko naman nakikita si Cap eh, ay SK hindi ko maramdaman ang SK, bakit may SK pa eh wala naman ginagawa dito “

3.2. In what ways did unfinished or delayed projects affect the overall condition of the community?

" Wala din, kase wala naman akong pakielam sa kanila eh. Pero kung meron silang ginawa, pwede maka apekto yon sa community at pwede din hindi rin makatulong kase wala nga eh. "

4.1. What do you think are the main obstacles preventing the successful implementation of these projects?

“Dito pag may kakilala ka sa barangay yun lang yung nabibigyan nila.”

4.2. In your view, does transparency play a role in project gaps? Please explain.

“Yan ang importante sa ngayon, kailangan transparent kung saan ginagamit ang pera”

5.1. How have these development projects affected your trust in the local government?

“wala nang tiwala, ang gusto ko lang mapalitan yung mga nakaupo sa barangay para may pagbabago.”

5.2. How do these experiences shape your overall perception of governance in Barangay 175?

“boring”

6.1. What improvements would you recommend for future Sustainable Development Projects?

"Gusto ko lang.. Yung curfew"

6.2. If you were given the opportunity, what project would you prioritize for Barangay 175 and why?

"Sa mga bata (curfew)"

Respondent 3

1.1. What Sustainable Development Projects are you aware of in Barangay 175?

"Ang alam ko lang naglilinis sila every friday, saturday about kalinisan, 5k once a year educational assistance"

1.2. In your opinion, do these projects address the real needs of the community? Why or why not?

"Hindi, ang nakatira sa Brgy. 175 hindi ramdam ng tao, hindi lahat nakaka-avail mga ginagawa na programa"

2.1. Can you describe your personal experience with the implementation of these projects?

"Malaking bagay. malaking bagay yung 5k sa student lalong lalo na sa mga kabataan na naghihikahos. Oo magagamit sa expenses. Hindi sa sapat, 5k lang yun eh. Eh dalawang sem lang tayo sa isang taon. Dapat twice."

2.2. What challenges have you personally experienced in relation to these projects?

"Hindi ko talaga ramdam project ng barangay, kalimitan kasi puro city yan eh. City nagbaba, puro project natin puro city. Sa barangay, hindi ko nakikita naong project ng barangay, nakikita ko lang ay project ng city hall. Gaya ng mga drainage. Mga kalsada na yan, tapos mga health center, eh city hall mga ano yan. Financial assistance lang yung alam ko na, pero iba wala akong nakikita."

3.1. Have you observed any projects that were delayed, discontinued, or inconsistently implemented? Please describe.

" Hindi ko masabi kung project ng barangay, kade kung pagbabasihan naten ang proyecy ng barangay, wala akong nakikita kase ang kalimitan na binababa is galing National, kung hindi National galing sa City. "

3.2. In what ways did unfinished or delayed projects affect the overall condition of the community?

" Sa basura na yan, meron na silang truck dati dito kaso hindi naman nag f function. "

4.1. What do you think are the main obstacles preventing the successful implementation of these projects?

"Sa leadership kasi nandyan naman yung budget, nandyan naman lahat. Wala paring implementation."

4.2. In your view, does transparency play a role in project gaps? Please explain.

"May transparency... nakita niyo yung bulletin board doon... pero in actual nandon ba?"

5.1. How have these development projects affected your trust in the local government?

"wala na akong trust."

5.2. How do these experiences shape your overall perception of governance in Barangay 175?

"pag ni rate natin 1 to 100, siguro 50."

6.1. What improvements would you recommend for future Sustainable Development Projects?

"Educational assistance, taasan nila, sa college dapat dyan twice yan. "

6.2. If you were given the opportunity, what project would you prioritize for Barangay 175 and why?

"Peace and Order, lawakan. Gawing accessible lahat ng covered court."

Respondent 4

1.1. What Sustainable Development Projects are you aware of in Barangay 175?

"Wala, ayuda. Yun lang alam ko"

1.2. In your opinion, do these projects address the real needs of the community? Why or why not?

"Slight lang siguro. Siguro sa iba, Hindi nakaka-abot. Hindi effective, Hindi equal sa pagbibigay"

2.1. Can you describe your personal experience with the implementation of these projects?

"Wala, buti pa nga ang SK ng barangay naanohan namin kaysa sa mismong barangay. Kay mayor ang ayuda, pero sa mismong kapitan ay di ko alam yung mga project na inimplement niya. Naririnig ko yung nakakahingi sa baranagay yung sa abuloy. Yung burolan dyan, alam ko city yan. Yun lang naman alam ko. Sa mga tanod nga rin, di yan nararamdaman dito. May once na nangyari, kumbaga may nagrariot na. Walang reresponse na tanod. Hindi nabibigyan information."

2.2. What challenges have you personally experienced in relation to these projects?

"Pagkakaroon ng pagbabago, meron dapat siyang forum ba. Pagdating diyan sa mga papel papel, okay nam an at mabilis siya. Wala namang ano kasi di naman sila naniningil. In terms of requirements, maayos naman siya."

3.1. Have you observed any projects that were delayed, discontinued, or inconsistently implemented? Please describe.

" Ang nagawa lang na nakita ko is itong sa kanal, eh National naman ang may hawak niyan eh . Very supportive naman si cap sa mga teachers sa elementary school kapag may program. "

3.2. In what ways did unfinished or delayed projects affect the overall condition of the community?

" Meron man kaya lang hindi naman namin nakikita, kase ang katwiran nila is malapit kame sa isang politician. Nakakapunta lang kame sa barangay kapag kukuha ng papel."

4.1. What do you think are the main obstacles preventing the successful

implementation of these projects?

“Corruption, yun ang number one... kasi magkukulang ang pondo kapag ganon... putol putol yung pag implement.”

4.2. In your view, does transparency play a role in project gaps? Please explain.

“Oo importante yan, para alam ng mga nasasakupan yung kilos sa loob ng barangay.”

5.1. How have these development projects affected your trust in the local government?

“parang wala na nga kaming pakielam... ultimo maliit na bagay tulad ng ayuda nilalagpasan kami.”

5.2. How do these experiences shape your overall perception of governance in Barangay 175?

“kailangan ng malaking pagbabago.”

6.1. What improvements would you recommend for future Sustainable Development Projects?

"Peace and Order nga at garbage collection."

6.2. If you were given the opportunity, what project would you prioritize for Barangay 175 and why?

"Ayusin ang Peace and Order"

Respondent 5

1.1. What Sustainable Development Projects are you aware of in Barangay 175?

"Barangay? Wala masyado (more on meetings sila mga heads), more on SK meron seminar nakakatulong HIV awareness seminar ex.)"

1.2. In your opinion, do these projects address the real needs of the community? Why or why not?

"Hindi"

2.1. Can you describe your personal experience with the implementation of these projects?

“Parang wala kasi akong nararamdaman na projects, kaya wala akong mabigay na opinion. Pero mas nanghihinayang ako kasi sobrang dami nilang pwedeng gawin throughout na nakaupo sila pero parang di lahat natutupad at parang di lahat nakakatanggap ng gan'on.”

2.2. What challenges have you personally experienced in relation to these projects?

“Wala naman masyado.”

3.1. Have you observed any projects that were delayed, discontinued, or inconsistently implemented? Please describe.

“Sa may educational assistance namen, na kahit naturuloy siya is may times na nire re-schedule. May nakikita din akong Health Center, pero walang mgq tao so anong silbi non? “

3.2. In what ways did unfinished or delayed projects affect the overall condition of the community?

"Madaming tao ang nahihirapan kapag hindi naayos yung lugar nila. Sa may Matarik o Robes, binabaha sila kapag malakas yung ulan, so throughout that day ang iisipin nila is kung papaano sila makakalikas.

4.1. What do you think are the main obstacles preventing the successful implementation of these projects?

“Yung una is corruption... napapansin ko syempre ang laki ng lugar natin so syempre malaki rin yung budget dyaan.”

4.2. In your view, does transparency play a role in project gaps? Please explain.

“Sa tingin ko wala... nagkaroon sila ng inauguration pero wala yung kapitan.”

5.1. How have these development projects affected your trust in the local government?

kung maganda yung naibibigay sa inyo may trust ka sa kanila... pero once nawala yung consistency nila sa projects, unti-unting nababawasan ang tiwala.”

5.2. How do these experiences shape your overall perception of governance in Barangay 175?

“dun kasi ako nag ojt (sa barangay)...so sa experience ko doon parang nakikita ko talaga yung corruption. Ang nangyare kasi nagkaroon ng bigayan ng bigas then ang unang nakakakuha doon is yung mga barangay officials.”

6.1. What improvements would you recommend for future Sustainable Development Projects?

"Unahin ang pagkakaayos ng mga binabahang lugar (flood control). Yung mga ayuda is dapat natatangap ng mga mamamayan mismo at sapat, hindi kulang-kulang."

6.2. If you were given the opportunity, what project would you prioritize for Barangay 175 and why?

"Gumawa ng health care (center) na kapag kailangan is makakapagbigay agad ng mga gamot."

Respondent 6

1.1. What Sustainable Development Projects are you aware of in Barangay 175?

“Clean-up drive, Kalinisan program (every week/month), healthcare free check-ups, pagpapatayo health centers”

1.2. In your opinion, do these projects address the real needs of the community? Why or why not?

"Maybe at some point natutugunan siya, sana nga nagagawa.. hindi lang puro social media posting"

2.1. Can you describe your personal experience with the implementation of these projects?

“Hindi kasi talaga ako active sa mga barangay programs, more on sa SK ako active. Sa SK, masasabi kong mas improved yung SK namin compared sa mismong nasa barangay. Doon sa mga sustainable activities ng barangay mismo. Di siya nasosobrang nai-implement ng maayos kasi palaging feel ko may kulang, feel ko may maiimprove pa yun. Feel ko may mas mata-tap pa silang maraming tao. Hindi lang sa certain area. Minsan mas natutugunan nila kung sino ‘yung mas malapit sa kanila or kung sino kapanig nila. Mas makakagawa sila ng maraming programs na marami pa silang mata-tap pero lagi nilang nadi-disregard yun. Lahat na lang ng activities or programs,

nakadepende na lang sa activities nila or program. Parang lagi na lang more on political”

2.2. What challenges have you personally experienced in relation to these projects?

“Pagdating d’on sa mga relief goods, mga cash assistance, mga goods from the city. ‘Di lahat ng resident ay nata-tap. Nata-tap kung sino ang mas malakas, kung sino mas may kapit. May mga taong nangangailangan ng tulong. May mga taong nasa rural areas na mas kailangan ang bagay na ‘yun. Kung sino ‘yung mga kapit, may kaya sa buhay or access sa mga resources na yun ay lagi silang nakakatanggap pero etong mga nasa rural ay hindi. Kasi nababasa ko yung mga issues na di sila nakakatanggap or napupuntahan ng mga projects. Feel ko ayun yung kulang.”

3.1. Have you observed any projects that were delayed, discontinued, or inconsistently implemented? Please describe.

" Every friday pumupunta sila Palmera para maglinis ilog pero hindi nila napagpatuloy. Kapag makikita mo sobrang dumi, kapag dadaan ka doon sobrang baho, so paano na lang yung mga dumadaan don. Siyempre dapat ma maintain nila yung protection or safety ng mgs tao na nakatira dito sa barangay at kung sino man yung bibisista dito. Kailangan din natin i maintain yung image, ikaw as polotician is nagre reflect yung characteristics mo or kung gaano ka ka-good leader doon san ipinapakita or maipapakita mo sa kaayusan ng community. "

3.2. In what ways did unfinished or delayed projects affect the overall condition of the community?

" Sobrang risky ng ganon eh, makita mo madumi yung kapaligiran mo tapos mabaho is parang mawawalan siguro sila nh gana. I just hope na makakapag reflect yung mga tao sa nakikita nila hindi yung patulou na magbubulag-bulagan sila. "

4.1. What do you think are the main obstacles preventing the successful implementation of these projects?

“Sila mismo, yung officials mismo... sila yung pipirma, sila yung makakapag implement pero they choose not to.”

4.2. In your view, does transparency play a role in project gaps? Please explain.

“Yes, pero dito wala namang transparency... wala kang makikitang sobrang transparent sa fundings.”

5.1. How have these development projects affected your trust in the local government?

“sobrang nakakaapekto siya sakín negatively... kasi hindi ako student na walang pakialam sa nangyayari sa pamumuno.”

5.2. How do these experiences shape your overall perception of governance in Barangay 175?

“lumaki ako bilang student leader kaya mataas yung standard ko sa pamumuno.”

6.1. What improvements would you recommend for future Sustainable Development Projects?

“Be consistent to their own projects.”

6.2. If you were given the opportunity, what project would you prioritize for Barangay 175 and why?

“Informal Labors, like street vendors, registration process and designated spaces for them.”

Respondent 7

1.1. What Sustainable Development Projects are you aware of in Barangay 175?

“Wala akong nakikitang projects, may nagawa about kalsada pero 10 years bago nagawa”

1.2. In your opinion, do these projects address the real needs of the community? Why or why not?

“Siguro sa project na yun (about kalsada), yes.”

2.1. Can you describe your personal experience with the implementation of these projects?

“Siguro ‘yung mga buildings na ginagawa ngayon, parang nai-iba lagi ‘yung time na matatapos sila. Lalo na yung multipurpose hall, nauurong na nauurong.”

2.2. What challenges have you personally experienced in relation to these projects?

“Siguro ‘yung ingay kasi tuwing gabi, malapit sa bahay namin. Super ingay. Another thing, yung parang stage sa may court, nag iba siya so yung mga nagzuzumba dun which is kasama tita ko, nagzuzumba siya sa kabilang stage kasi dalawa yung stage d’on.”

3.1. Have you observed any projects that were delayed, discontinued, or inconsistently implemented? Please describe.

" Yung regarding sa Multi purpose Hall na umuuronh yung paggawa, pero alam ko dapat this year siya matatapos. "

3.2. In what ways did unfinished or delayed projects affect the overall condition of the community?

" Maingay siya tuwing gabi or every time na may ginagawa sila, so ang nangyayari sa mga tao is hindi sila makatulog agad. "

4.1. What do you think are the main obstacles preventing the successful implementation of these projects?

“Corruption, di na yan mawawala.”

4.2. In your view, does transparency play a role in project gaps? Please explain.

“Kung transparent sila malalaman ng bawat tao kung tugma ba yung nagastos nila sa project.”

5.1. How have these development projects affected your trust in the local government?

“kawawa yung mga tao na dapat pagserbisyuhan.”

5.2. How do these experiences shape your overall perception of governance in Barangay 175?

“hindi ko gusto ang pamamahala ng ating kapitan dahil sa gaps sa pamamahala.”

6.1. What improvements would you recommend for future Sustainable Development Projects?

"Transparency and mas maagap na pagpapagawa ng mga infrastructures at mas maayos na governance."

6.2. If you were given the opportunity, what project would you prioritize for Barangay 175 and why?

"Inclusivity sa privileges para mas mafeel natin na included and lahat."

Respondent 8

1.1. What Sustainable Development Projects are you aware of in Barangay 175?

"Free medical check-ups weekly, may nabasa about clean-up drive"

1.2. In your opinion, do these projects address the real needs of the community? Why or why not?

"At some point yes, especially medical and clean-up"

2.1. Can you describe your personal experience with the implementation of these projects?

"Well as a resident, well implemented ito pero limited yung mga nakakakuha ng mga service na to. Pero actually di lahat ng 175 ay natutulungan so medyo lacking resources nila."

2.2. What challenges have you personally experienced in relation to these projects?

"Ayun madalas may kulang sila sa resources. I've once na kasi akong lumapit sa barangay for my assistance for anti-rabies and wala silang resources which is a necessity for a booster shot. Ayun kulang sila sa kagamitan at gamot. Nonetheless ayun lang naman nakikita ko."

3.1. Have you observed any projects that were delayed, discontinued, or inconsistently implemented? Please describe.

" Maraming problema lalo ma sa road here in 175, hindi agad naayos ng barangay although hindi sila ang main responsibility taker but meron padin silang i take na action."

3.2. In what ways did unfinished or delayed projects affect the overall condition of the community?

" Sa may Camarin to NHA area, medyo hassle yung pag travel around this area "

4.1. What do you think are the main obstacles preventing the successful implementation of these projects?

"Yung barangay itself is hindi masyadong coordinated... they lack people para maayos na mag flow yung mga project."

4.2. In your view, does transparency play a role in project gaps? Please explain.

"Yes and no... pinapakita nila but not all of it."

5.1. How have these development projects affected your trust in the local government?

"medyo trashy ang perceptions and trust ko sa kanila kasi sobrang daming pwede pang gawin pero hindi naa-address."

5.2. How do these experiences shape your overall perception of governance in Barangay 175?

"I would give it a rating of 6 or 7 out of 10... may good projects pero kulang pa sa resources."

6.1. What improvements would you recommend for future Sustainable Development Projects?

"Kumuha ng mga sponsors para mapunan ang mga resources."

6.2. If you were given the opportunity, what project would you prioritize for Barangay 175 and why?

"Coordination for Garbage Collection"

Respondent 9

1.1. What Sustainable Development Projects are you aware of in Barangay 175?

"Yung mga nililinis at pinagawang creek"

1.2. In your opinion, do these projects address the real needs of the community? Why or why not?

"Hindi kasi kahit ginawa na (creek) bumabaha parin, sa tingin ko dapat mas nagfocus sila sa tamang pagtatapon ng basura"

2.1. Can you describe your personal experience with the implementation of these projects?

"Parang okay naman, nakakalinis naman din sila kaso same process lang everyday. Linis sa umaga, nagkakalat maghapon ang nga resident and repeat."

2.2. What challenges have you personally experienced in relation to these projects?

"Wala naman"

3.1. Have you observed any projects that were delayed, discontinued, or inconsistently implemented? Please describe.

" Doon naman sa sampaguita, dapat last 2 months pa dapat tapos yun sa pagkakaalam ko pero ngayon pa lang sinimulan ang pagawa. "

3.2. In what ways did unfinished or delayed projects affect the overall condition of the community?

" Naging maputik ang daan pag umulan at sumikip din ang mga daanan dahil sa mga gamit nila sa construction. "

4.1. What do you think are the main obstacles preventing the successful implementation of these projects?

"Tinipid ang budget kaya napakatagal matapos at substandard ang materials."

4.2. In your view, does transparency play a role in project gaps? Please explain.

"Kulang sila sa transparency."

5.1. How have these development projects affected your trust in the local government?

“pumangit ang tiwala kasi dito sa 175 pagpasok at pag-uwi traffic lagi... sayang sa oras.”

5.2. How do these experiences shape your overall perception of governance in Barangay 175?

“araw-araw akong dumadaan sa kalsadang pinagawa nila... naaalala ko kung paano nila tinipid at niloko ang mga tao.”

6.1. What improvements would you recommend for future Sustainable Development Projects?

"Mabilis maayos at mabisang paraan ng pag collection ng mga basura sa daan. para mas maluwag ang kalsada at walang bumara sa irrigation at hindi mag cost ng traffic pag umuulan."

6.2. If you were given the opportunity, what project would you prioritize for Barangay 175 and why?

"Urban planning, tamang plano at angkop base sa location na housing project para sa may maayos na mga kalsada luluwag maayos na drainage tapos yung segregation about sa basura para hindi tapon ng tapon kung saan saan. kung nagkaroon ng urban planning dati sa barangay 175 caloocan sigurado walang traffic baha at perwisyong mga kalat kung saan saan. "

Respondent 10

1.1. What Sustainable Development Projects are you aware of in Barangay 175?

“Kalinisan sa Bagong Pilipinas Program”

1.2. In your opinion, do these projects address the real needs of the community? Why or why not?

"Not really, kadalasan naglilinis lang sila ng kalsada tuwing umaga. Mas maganda kung nagkakaroon ng system or policies na magpo-prohibit sa mga residents sa pagkakalat, pagtatapon sa kalsada."

2.1. Can you describe your personal experience with the implementation of these projects?

“Nagka-traffic noon kasi one way ‘yung kalsada noong ginagawa nila yung creek.”

2.2. What challenges have you personally experienced in relation to these projects?

“D’yan sa barugo robes, kahit bagong gawa yung mga drainage bumabaha pa rin kasi puro basura. kaya ayun bumabara at kaya maraming sasakyan ang na-stranded pag dumaan d’yan.”

3.1. Have you observed any projects that were delayed, discontinued, or inconsistently implemented? Please describe.

" So far, in my best knowledge wala naman. "

3.2. In what ways did unfinished or delayed projects affect the overall condition of the community?

N/A

4.1. What do you think are the main obstacles preventing the successful implementation of these projects?

“Iba kasi ang goal ng mga politika... not long term growth but just making impression sa tao.”

4.2. In your view, does transparency play a role in project gaps? Please explain.

“People should know bakit may ganon para they can support or give comment for improvement.”

5.1. How have these development projects affected your trust in the local government?

“when I see elected officials who act for the community and not only for themselves, they gain my trust.”

5.2. How do these experiences shape your overall perception of governance in Barangay 175?

“okay naman, may mga project that really help people.”

6.1. What improvements would you recommend for future Sustainable Development Projects?

"Look for project na for long term sustainability."

6.2. If you were given the opportunity, what project would you prioritize for Barangay 175 and why?

" I would prioritize project about kalinisan, karamihan ng mga tao sa Caloocan are complaining about basura. But the problem is the same community is the one na nagkakalat rin, I would create a system na magwork both sa mga garbage collectors as well as sa mga residents na di napapasukan ng trucks because sa iskinita or pathwalks sila nakatira."

Appendix C

Documentation

BIONOTE

Winston P. Morales is a Bachelor of Science in Human Resource Management at the University of Caloocan City. He has a strong interest in organizational development, employee relations, and sustainable community practices. As a researcher, he contributed to the process of creating the research from Chapter 1 to Chapter 5., aiming to understand community perceptions and support meaningful development initiatives.

Maria Veronica S. Botial is a 3rd year college student taking the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration (BSBA) major in Human Resource Management at the University of Caloocan City (UCC). She is one of the researchers who contributed to the development of various parts of the study. Her academic interests include human resource management, organizational development, and community development.

Jashkleish Gonzaga is a Bachelor of Science in Human Resource Management student at the University of Caloocan City. She has a growing interest in community development, social awareness, and sustainable practices. As a researcher, she contributed to the completion of the study from Chapter 1 to Chapter 5, focusing on understanding the perceptions regarding the effects of sustainable development and importance of inclusive and meaningful community-based initiatives.

Azell Ann A. Diamse is a Human Resource Management student at the University of Caloocan City. She is one of the researchers behind the study titled “Voices from the Margins: How the People of Barangay 175 Perceive the Effects of Sustainable Development,” which aims to understand community perspectives in order to promote more effective and inclusive sustainable development initiatives.

James Rofel T. Naing is a 3rd Year college student from the University of Caloocan City taking the course of Bachelor of Science Major In Human Resource Management. He has experience in conducting qualitative research studies that focus on social issues, governance, and the lived experiences of local communities. He is one of the researchers of the study titled “Voices from the Margins: How the People of Barangay 175 Perceive the Effects of Sustainable Development.”